

Report D3.4

“First report on domain ontology requirements
and specifications”

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Report D3.4

“First report on domain ontology requirements and specifications”

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Executive Summary

OntoCommons aims at working towards interoperability by means of harmonization with respect to upper-level ontologies and facilitating agreement in domain ontology development. As part of the effort of work package 3, an objective of OntoCommons is to collect and formalize requirements from the stakeholders' community by domain in terms of ontology development and exploitation. This report presents a set of functional and non-functional requirements based on the needs of demonstrators but also from stakeholders' (including domain experts') inputs - from inside and outside the project - collected through a set of expert group meetings and workshops. This deliverable (D3.4) is the first report on the collection of such requirements. This deliverable will serve as input for the investigation of intra- and cross-domain interoperability in Task 3.4, as well as for the ontology knowledge graph validation in Task 4.6.

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1. Introduction

Work package 3 (WP3) of the OntoCommons project aims at intra- and cross-domain interoperability by harmonizing domain ontologies. The Task 3.3 of the WP3 specifically focuses on reviewing and formalizing common requirements for a standardized suite of domain ontologies, the latter including both newly developed and existing ontologies in domains such as materials modelling and manufacturing. As proposed by OntoCommons, the requirements will be formed not only based on the needs of demonstrators but also from stakeholders' (including domain experts') inputs - from inside and outside the project - collected through a set of expert group meetings and workshops. This deliverable (D3.4) is the first report on the collection of such requirements. Overall, the scope and purpose of the deliverable are presented in the following sections (1.1 and 1.2). This particular task is dependent on the results from other tasks of OntoCommons. At the same time, the outcome of this task will also provide valuable input for other tasks. The interdependency between these tasks is described in section 1.3. The remaining of the report consists of section 2 to describe the methodology used for collecting the requirements, section 3 to present the non-functional requirements, section 4 to present the functional requirements, section 5 to provide the evaluation of the sets of requirements, and section 6 for the conclusion.

1.1 Purpose of deliverable

The deliverable focuses on the review and formalization of common requirements for ontology specifications and exploitation from different applications (demonstrators) and domain (listed in Section 2.4) level points of view. In particular, the deliverable captures stakeholders' inputs about their requirements and needs from a domain ontology perspective. Requirements include specifications of each domain ontology, the core capabilities (e.g., competency questions) and specific perspectives of exploitations of the domain.

1.2 Scope of deliverable

The deliverable captures ontology requirements in domains such as materials and manufacturing as needed by the demonstrators and agreed upon by the wider community of stakeholders. In this report, only some sub-areas under materials and manufacturing are considered. The list of these sub-areas is given in Section 2.4.

1.3 Relation among work packages and deliverables

Figure 1 shows an overview of the inputs of this deliverable; this includes tasks from WP4 and WP5. As illustrated, T3.3 activities consider the needs of the use cases that are expressed in 'D5.2 specification of initial cases', and it is based on the results of D3.1 'report on communities interested in domain-specific semantics', D3.2 'Domain-specific semantic landscape' and D4.2 'methodological framework for ontology management'. Furthermore, this deliverable will serve as input for the

investigation of intra- and cross-domain interoperability in T3.4, as well as for the ontology knowledge graph validation in T4.6.

Figure 1: Overview of the inputs/outputs of D3.4 'First report on domains ontology requirements and specifications'

2. Methodology

The requirement engineering for ontologies has been widely described by different authors as part of different proposed methodologies for ontology engineering. A comprehensive state of the art review for ontology engineering life cycle that prescribes methodologies for different phases of ontology engineering, from requirement definitions to ontology maintenance, as well as techniques, and tools to support these activities, is presented in the report "D4.2 - Methodological framework for ontology management". This latter report proposes the Linked Open Terms (LOT) methodology as the recommended one for OntoCommons by displaying its advantages over other methodologies by an evaluation based on seven criteria, i.e., 1) completeness, 2) FAIRness, 3) re usability, 4) collaborativeness, 5) applicability, 6) agility and 7) modularity (see Table 1 of D4.2). The requirement analysis, conducted as part of Task 3.3, closely follows the LOT recommendations. However, considering the wide scope and purpose of OntoCommons, some adjustments to the methodology are implemented through agreement within the WP3 partners to take into account the variety of domains and demonstrators being analysed.

The LOT methodology is an agile and iterative ontology development methodology that includes four activities: 1) ontology requirements specification, 2) ontology implementation, 3) ontology publication and 4) ontology maintenance. The LOT methodology is based on the NeOn methodology

(Figuroa, 2009) and it adapts previous ontology development processes from the European projects VICINITY¹, BIMERR², DELTA³, and EasyTV⁴ to the particularities of OntoCommons. Figure 2 is borrowed from D4.2 to present in more detail the steps for the first phase of ontology engineering, that is, the requirement specification.

Figure 2: Ontology requirements specification sub-activities

As the first step of requirements specification proposed by LOT, the vision of the potential use of the ontology needs to be captured by a set of use cases. This activity involves domain experts, users, and ontology engineers to formalize a list of use cases describing situations that are desired to be reached with the data described by the ontology. In the context of the OntoCommons project, the requirement engineering effort is not about building ontologies for one particular task or domain, but to harmonise existing domain ontologies for materials and manufacturing, as well as to building new ontologies for areas that are not yet covered by suitable ontologies. Furthermore, OntoCommons has 11 initial demonstrators that allow project partners to foster the development of initial guidelines and best practices driven by common requirements with regards to ontologies and tools. The initial demonstrators are mainly from the Materials, Manufacturing and Procurement domains. Therefore, the proposed LOT methodology for ontology requirement engineering needs to be reoriented in these three different aspects.

¹ <http://vicinity.iot.linkeddata.es/vicinity/>

² <https://bimerr.eu/bimerr-tools/bimerr-ontology-network/>

³ <http://delta.iot.linkeddata.es/>

⁴ <https://oeg-upm.github.io/easytv-onto/OnToology/ontology/core.ttl/documentation/index-en.html>

2.1 Workflow

In this section, we describe the steps in the three phases of requirement engineering performed to construct the domain level requirements as part of T3.3. The three phases are described in three following sub sections, each associated with a figure depicting the corresponding workflow in flowcharts. Figure 2 presents the overall three phases with off-page references to be expanded later and the description for the flowchart elements used in this report.

Figure 3: Three phases of domain ontology requirement engineering

2.1.1 Collecting requirements from use cases

In this section, the steps of collecting requirements from the use cases are described in detail. The workflow is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 4: Phase 1 of requirement engineering – collecting requirements from use cases.

The beginning of the process started with an internal meeting between members of the WP3 and WP5 to prepare and arrange interviews with all industrial partners (labelled as 'use case owner' hereafter) who contributed to at least one use case within OntoCommons. It was decided that the interviews were to be conducted to provide input to both this requirement gathering activity performed by WP3 as well as deliverable D5.2: *Specification of initial use cases* to be edited by WP5 (T5.2). The interview questions, presented in Section 11, were designed to address both concerns. Members from both the WP3 and WP5 agreed on a schedule for personalized interviews in a way that, along with the representative from use case owner, at least one member from T3.3, one member from T5.2, and one use case partner (some OntoCommons consortium members who assist the use case owner in the communication with the project) for each use case will be present for each interview. Members from T5.2 coordinated with the participants to schedule the interviews as per their availability.

Before each interview, the use case owner was asked to complete the interview questions as much as possible so that any clarification on the questions and expected answers needed by the use case owner could be addressed during the interview. During the interview, the WP3 member asked for more details on the specifications of the use case to have a better understanding. Based on the answers to the interview questions provided by the use case owner and the discussions that occurred during the interview, 'Ontology Requirement Specification Document' (ORSD) (see Section 2.2), including scope, purpose, a set of non-functional requirements, a set of functional requirements, and a list 20 most important terms^{5,6}, along with other details, was prepared for each use case. Each ORSD document was sent back to the corresponding use case owner and partner for verification and amended either by the WP3 members based on comments provided or directly by use case owners and partners. This step was repeated until the use case owner or the partner confirmed its completion (see Disclaimer A).

After the ORSD document for a use case is completed, the functional requirements collected from the use case were analysed to extract a set of terms along with the top-20 terms submitted by the use case owner during the interview. Each term in this glossary was also adorned with synonyms, meronyms, hyponyms and associated domain areas (please see the enlisted topics in Section 2.4).

2.1.2 *Analysing requirements for domain areas*

This phase of requirement engineering was started after the requirements specific to all use cases are collected completely. As we described before, the use cases do not directly correspond to the domain as requirements related to a particular domain can be found in multiple use cases. In this phase, we aim to collate the use case requirements for a specific domain area and expand them to increase coverage of that domain. Before we explain the steps performed for this phase requirement engineering, the purpose and the scope of this step are explained in more detail below.

Each of the domain areas is broad and can be viewed from many perspectives from the application's point of view. The demonstration cases only concern some of these views. Naturally, it is not possible to come up with a complete set of requirements covering all the areas from just the use case

⁵ The number was decided in consensus with the stakeholders from WP3 and WP5 balancing the workload on the demonstrator and sufficient terms for capturing a complete model.

⁶ Here 'term' refers to a single word. The notion behind of the term may be specific to the application areas for a particular use case. Such elucidations needs to be derived from the use case descriptions.

requirements. Even when some requirements exist for a particular topic, the use case requirements fail to capture the complete model for that topic. Therefore, the purpose of this phase is to first, complete each topic mentioned in the use case requirement and second, explore new requirements for the areas/sub-areas/aspects that are not covered by the requirements from the use cases. For example, let's assume use cases mention four requirements (in terms of competency question) regarding *plant*: "What is the design specification of a plant?", "What are the components of a plant?", "What are the functions of the plant?", and "Who are the stakeholders of the plant?". To complete the description of the Factory, some other topics, such as the plant layout (or factory layout), how is plant layout is related to flow or job shop and the relationships with asset and/or resources are also required to be modelled. New areas of application may be explored for some topics that have use case requirements only focusing on the practice of a single industry. For example, if processes for laser cutting is mentioned in the use case requirement, then other cutting operations used in different industries also need to be added to form a complete domain-level requirement for the cutting process.

Although the competency questions add more specifications to the terms, going in the direction of better defining the concept. However, the answers are usually implicitly referred to the specific domain terminology and make no use of more rigorous ontological concepts as usually found in TLO/MLO. The idea of proposing in WP2 some pre-defined reference concepts to which DLO ontology developers can refer to and understand, can be useful since it would provide ways for a better elucidation of DLO terms. Therefore, it is recommended that ontology developers to first rephrase the competency questions and their answers with predefined set of terms (to be supplied by WP2).

Figure 5: Expansion of use case requirements to find the domain level requirement for expected coverage

At the same time, it will take a huge amount of time to address all possible topics in a domain concerning every possible viewpoint and granularity. This is also not a productive effort as those requirements could not be validated without related data and demonstration cases. For this reason,

it is critical to find the right scope for such domain level requirements. Informally, the use case requirements collected from the demonstrators for each domain may look like the dashed line shapes in orange, shown in Figure 5, due to the narrowed focus of the use cases. The goal is to find the set of domain requirements that covers all the use case requirements (green solid line) along with the gaps among them. However, the scope of the domain requirements should neither overstretch (red solid line) as these extra requirements will be hard to validate nor under cover (orange solid line) as then some of the demonstrator requirements will not be covered in terms of requirement.

The steps of analysing requirements for specific domain areas are described in detail. The workflow is presented in Figure 4.

The first step of this phase is to identify the domain areas to be addressed in the requirement analysis. The list of domain areas was agreed upon by the task members based on the domain areas identified during the landscape analysis conducted under T3.2, inputs from community input collected in the focused workshops conducted as part of T3.1, as well as the priority imposed by the scopes and focus of the use cases. This list of the domain areas and the justification of such choice are given in Section 4.2.

Next, for each domain area, the functional requirements are collected from different use cases using the glossary of terms as reference. In this strategy, the term in the glossary is first tagged with the domain areas. Then all the terms for a domain area are filtered. With the help of the reference of competency questions from which each term is extracted, all the competency questions relevant to the domain area is collected from the list of terms for that domain area. It is to be noted, this process may assign the same functional requirement to multiple domain areas as one term may be tagged with more than one domain area. This is justified by the fact that there are certain overlaps among the domain areas. Section 2.2 describes the template of the glossary and the ORSD document in which the domain level requirements are maintained. We provide an example of this collation process below.

Let's assume the term "X" is tagged with the domain areas D. At the same time this term is extracted from functional requirement 1 of use case 1, 2 of use case 2, and 3 of use case 3. Therefore, functional requirements 1-1, 2-2, and 3-3 are assigned to ORSD documents dedicated to domain area D.

Figure 6: Phase 2 of requirement engineering – analysing requirements for domain areas

After this collation process, a set of ORSD documents are formed, each of which contains the partial requirements for a specific domain area. Next, we organized a series of expert group meetings, which were participated by domain experts, both internal and external to the OntoCommons project. For each of the meetings, we provided the members with a set of functional requirements and a list of terms as the foundation for further exploration. The inputs were collected as direct input from the expert or through detailed discussion and collaboration through online conceptualization exercises. These activities also included deliberation on the agreement for a suitable purpose and scope for each specific domain. More details on these expert group meetings are given in Section 2.3.

At the final steps of this phase, the set of functional requirements for a domain was checked for completion, that if they address all aspects of the domain under the scope and if not, then the domain experts were asked to add more requirements to address the missing aspect. This test is among other completion criteria, which are described in Section 2.4. The other completion criteria were checked after it is determined that the set of functional requirements completely address all aspects of the specific domain. The other completion criteria may require some internal adjustment to the requirements, including rewriting for unambiguity, removal of duplicates, etc. Once the set of requirements for a domain was 'completed', that all completion criteria passed, then all the new terms from this domain level requirements are added to the existing list of terms in the glossary.

2.2 Templates

We defined a collaborative file sharing space to group all the required templates for collecting, annotating, and validating the use case and domain requirements. During our work, we followed the same patterns to keep tracking of different versions, facilitate mapping/link between the different use case specifications, and manage their completion. To structure the collected knowledge, we prepared interview questions and a UC requirements template in collaboration with WP5 members.

2.2.1 *List of questions for the UC specification interview*

To prepare the use case interviews, we specified a set of targeted open questions to be answered by the partners before the online meeting to better understand the use case specification. The document includes information about use case specification (pre/postcondition, the main involved actors, key steps of the main scenario, and most relevant 20 terms), implementation time plan (milestones or scenario step of the implementation), FAIR plan (level of FAIRness and next steps for improving the FAIR scores), Technology Readiness Levels (TRL), and key performance indicators (KPI) of the use case.

2.2.2 *Requirement template*

To collect each use case and domain knowledge requirement, we created a specific tabular template including two parts: first, the Ontology Requirements Specification Document (ORSD) (Suárez-Figueroa et al., 2009) proposed by the NeOn methodology (described in D4.2 (Fernandez Izquierdo & Poveda-Villalón, 2021)) for identifying general requirements mainly the purpose and scope. Second, ORSD UC Functional Requirements (FRs) contain information about the ontology content (i.e., specific classes, properties, and axioms that might be defined in an ontology); this template has been adapted to OntoCommons domain needs.

For collecting the non-functional requirements (general aspects related to ontology metadata or structure), we primarily focused on the first and second fields, “purpose” and “scope” that is mandatory to express the partners’ goal for building an ontology, and then on the other optional information concerning the implementation language, intended end-users, intended uses, and ontology requirements. Figure 7 shows an example of a completed ORSD template for AirBus use case UC1.

Ontology Requirements Specification Document	
1	Purpose (mandatory)
	The use case aims to demonstrate: - decreased development time via automatized decision making and improved re-usability, - improved reliability via traceability, - improved communication between product, assembly and industrial system experts via data integration and increased domain knowledge interoperability.
2	Scope (mandatory)
	Increase the interoperability and improve the communication between aircraft design, assembly design and the industrial system design
3	Implementation Language (optional)
4	Intended End-Users (optional)
	1) Knowledge scientist 2) System engineering expert 3) Assembly process engineer 4) Simulation engineer
5	Intended Uses
	The system is expected to support decision-making during aircraft industrial system design. Some expected benefits include: 1) Predict behavior, explore architectural alternatives early in the development process, and perform trade studies to assess which design choices make the most sense for manufacturing performance. 2) Develop a cognitive twin based on captured domain knowledge, models and simulations. 3) Perform a Business transformation that includes new organizations and new roles to develop the models and to perform manufacturing engineering activities.
6	Ontology Requirements
	1. Non-Functional Requirements
	This use case will be based on the output of a relevant project (QU4LITY) pilot. Another objective is to improve the interoperability by aligning the application ontology to the top level ontology or top reference ontology which are expected output of OntoCommons.
	1. Functional Requirements: Lists or tables of requirements written as Competency Questions and sentences
7	Pre-Glossary of Terms (optional)
	1. Terms from Competency Questions
	1. Terms from Answers
	1. Objects

Figure 7: An excerpt of a complete ORSD template from the Airbus use case

When collecting the functional ontology requirements, we suggest formalizing them as competency questions (as proposed by Gruninger and Fox) or natural language sentences (when it is possible we accompanied them by answers or expected results suggested by the partners) which are meant as queries that, once formally represented, an ontology should be able to answer. For tracking information about the competency questions, we created a particular tabular template for the adjusted ORSD FRs including the seven fields that are represented in Table 3.

Table 1: Structure of the adjusted ORSD Functional Requirements Template

Identifier	Sprint	CQ	Answer	Status	Provenance	Priority
Code (domain+id)	Code the sprint (UC-interview)	A question or an affirmative sentence	Words, sub-sentences, or a complete sentence	Accepted, rejected, pending or deprecated	Source of the collected CQ	High, medium, or low

- *Identifier*. The requirement identifier needs to be unique for each requirement,
- *Sprint*. The sprint of the requirement iteration,

- *CQ*: The competency question or natural language sentence,
- *Answer*: The answer to the competency question,
- *Status*: The status of the requirement might be: 1) proposed, 2) accepted, 3) rejected, 4) ongoing or 5) deprecated,
- *Provenance*: The provenance of the provided requirement (UC questions, interview, mail, etc.),
- *Priority*: The priority of the requirement can be: 1) high, 2) medium, or 3) low.

Figure 3 shows an example of ORSD functional UC functional requirements extracted from the Airbus use case. We note that the description of the priority was not easy to be specified by the demonstrators. Consequently, we ignored this field during this current ORSD version, but we plan to complete it in a later version.

Identifier (domain+id)	Sprint	Competency Question / Natural language sentence (fact)	Answer	Status (Proposed, Accepted, Rejected, Pending, Deprecated)
UC1-1	UC interview	What are the types of resource?	Human resource, intangible resource, material resource	Accepted
UC1-2	UC interview	What are the types of manufacturing resource?	Equipment, facilities	Accepted
UC1-3	UC interview	What are the types of equipment?	Drilling adapter, drilling template, measuring equipment, robot, fastener, wedge	Accepted
UC1-4	UC interview	What are the types of materials?	Manufacturing material, raw material, assembly	Accepted
UC1-5	UC interview	What are the component of an assembly?	None.	Accepted
UC1-6	UC interview	What are the types of assembly?	Front fuselage, rear fuselage	Accepted
UC1-7	UC interview	What are the types of part?	Buttstrap, fastener, frame, stabiliser, stringer	Accepted
UC1-8	UC interview	What are the functions for different resources?		Accepted
UC1-9	UC interview	What are the qualities of different resources?		Accepted
UC1-10	UC interview	What are the qualities of different materials?		Accepted
UC1-11	UC interview	What are the qualities of different processes?		Accepted
UC1-12	UC interview	What are the types of processes?	Boring, cleaning, deburring, drilling, fastening, fixing, insert, inspection, installation	Accepted
UC1-13	UC interview	What are the functions that are realized by different processes?		Accepted
UC1-14	UC interview	What are the required resources of different processes?		Accepted
UC1-15	UC interview	What are the required materials of different processes?		Accepted
UC1-16	UC interview	What are the information for a system requirement?	Design criteria, design rule, TLR	Accepted
UC1-17	UC interview	What are the types of system model?		Accepted
UC1-18	UC interview	What are the component of a system model?		Accepted
UC1-19	UC interview	What are the sub-processes of a design process?		Accepted
UC1-20	UC interview	What are the information for a process plan?		Accepted
UC1-21	UC interview	What are the information for system design?		Accepted

Figure 8: An excerpt of a complete ORSD Functional Requirements template created for the Airbus use case.

2.2.3 Glossary of terms (GT)

For identifying, analysing, and classifying the terms being defined in the CQs and answers, we created a glossary of terms⁷ table (A) for expressing general information about each term. The UC term index contains seven columns as described in Table 3: term, synonym (extracted from the Wordnet browser^{8,9}), related UC, related CQs, hyponym (term used to design a particular; a type of), meronym (term used to refer to a part; a part of), domain area, and all the CQs of all the studied domains that contain this term. For example, the term "process", the synonyms are procedure, operation, and action, the related UCS are UC 11, UC 12, UC 13, UC 14, UC 15, and UC 20, the hyponyms (extracted answers) are assembly process, business process, manufacturing operation, and the domain is manufacturing. Figure 5 shows the complete structure of the created term index. Appendix 1 shows the resulted glossary of terms (ordered from A to Z), it shows that the current version (V1) contains 163 simple terms.

⁷ The glossary of the terms does not contain their application and domain-specific elucidations.

⁸ <http://wordnetweb.princeton.edu/perl/webwn>

⁹ The Wordnet synonyms and definitions for these terms may not capture the actual notion for which the term is used in the domain or application. The elucidations need to be derived from the corresponding competency questions and related domain and application specific usage.

Table 2: Structure of the Glossary terms template

Term	Synonym(s)	UC	CQs	Hyponym	Meronym	Domain area	All UC CQ
The simple or composite word	One word or a list of words	One number (1 to 11)	List of numbers if the word is used in different CQs.	One word or a list of words	One word or a list of words	One or more values	List of referring contains the term CQs that the

Term	Wordnet synonym	UC	CQ	Hyponym (type of)	Meronym (part of)	Domain Area	All UC-CQ
Resource	none.	1	1,8,9,14	Human resource, intangible resource, material resource		Enterprise, Manufacturing	1Q1, 1Q2, 1Q8, 1Q9, 1Q14
Manufacturing Resource	none.	1	2	Equipment, facilities		Manufacturing	1Q2
Equipment	none.	1	3	Drilling adapter, drilling template, measuring equipment, rot		Manufacturing, System	1Q3, 2Q3, 2Q10, 2Q14, 2Q20, 4Q1, 10Q8
Material	stuff	1	4	Manufacturing material, raw material, assembly		Product, Manufacturing, Material	1Q4, 3Q11, 3Q13, 6Q6, 6Q7, 6Q12, 6Q15, 6Q21, 10Q6, 7Q2, 7Q10
Component	part, portion	1	5			Product, System	1Q5, 2Q7, 3Q3, 3Q12, 3Q7, 9Q23, 5Q7, 11Q5, 11Q15, 11Q25, 8Q13
Assembly	none.	1	5,6,25,30,32	Front fuselage, rear fuselage		Product, System	1Q5
Function	purpose, use, role	1	8,13			Manufacturing	1Q8, 1Q13, 3Q4, 9Q2, 11Q8
Quality	caliber, character	1	9,10,11			Manufacturing, Maintenance, System	1Q9, 1Q10, 1Q11, 3Q29, 4Q12->21, 7Q5
Process	procedure, operation, action	1	11,12,13,14,15,20,25	Assembly process, Business process, Manufacturing operati		Manufacturing	1Q11, 1Q12, 1Q13, 1Q14, 1Q15, 1Q20, 1Q25, 2Q1, 2Q2, 2Q4, 3Q11
Manufacturing operation		1		Boring, cleaning, deburring, drilling, fastening, fixing, insert, inspection, installation			*
Requirement	demand, necessity, requisite	1	16,32	Design criteria, design rule, TLR		Maintenance, Enterprise	1Q16, 1Q32, 3Q8, 3Q10, 3Q27
Information	data	1	16			Information	1Q16, 3Q10, 11Q14
Model	framework, pattern, mock up	1	18	System Model		Information, System	1Q18, 2Q6, 2Q8, 2Q9, 2Q17
Design	plan, pattern, blue print	1	19,21,22			Product, System	1Q19, 1Q21, 1Q22, 3Q1, 3Q11, 3Q12
System		1	16,17,18,22,24,30,32			System	1Q16, 1Q17, 1Q18, 1Q22, 1Q24, 1Q30, 1Q32, 9Q24, 11Q32, 11Q33
Plan	design, program	1	20	Manufacturing process plan		Manufacturing	1Q20, 1Q27
Actor	doer, worker	1	22	Knowledge scientist, System engineering expert, Assembly process engineer, Simulation engineer			1Q22, 2Q18, 9Q8, 10Q12, 10Q15, 10Q29, 7Q9, 11Q18
Role	function, office, part	1	23,24,25,26				1Q23, 1Q24, 1Q25, 1Q26
knowledge scientist	none.	1	23				*
Engineering	none.	1	24,26				1Q24, 1Q26, 3Q14, 3Q15, 3Q16, 11Q5
Expert	none.	1	24				1Q24
Engineer	applied scientist, technologist	1	25				1Q25
Simulation	none.	1	26				1Q26
Decision	determination, conclusion	1	28,29				1Q28, 1Q29
Product	merchandise, ware	1	31	Manufactured product			1Q31, 3Q6, 3Q7, 3Q12, 3Q22

Figure 9: An excerpt of the glossary of terms template for UC1. Selected simple terms are coloured in blue, in yellow we mentioned the composite terms.

2.3 Meeting and focus group format

Several steps of the requirement engineering are conducted in collaboration with members from other work packages, industrial demonstrators from OntoCommons as well as external experts. In this section, we describe three sets of meetings, which are a set of the focused group meeting to survey the domain landscape broadly, a set of meetings with use case owners and use case partners in collaboration with WP5 members, and a set of focused group meeting for deep exploration of the individual domain is for domain-level requirements. Apart from these meetings, WP3 task members met bi-weekly to discuss the progress of this effort and build strategy. These meetings are not included in this report, however minutes of meeting for each of these meetings are rigorously captured and stored in the internal archive.

Three group meetings were organized in May 2021 to gather some more ideas of the current shape of the domain ontology landscape and identify gaps. Unlike the DORIC-MM workshops, these meetings were conducted with smaller groups of domain experts and predefined domains in the scope of the discussion. The first meeting, held on May 20th, focused on Physics, Chemistry, and Material Science domain, whereas two separate meetings were held on May 26th and May 31st respectively focusing on Mechanical, Industrial, and Process engineering. All meetings were held online with a preselected group of invited experts from industry, academia, and research institutes.

Each meeting was held for two hours following a similar format. After a round of introduction, a short presentation was given to the participants outlining the agenda and scope of the meeting. The rest of the hours were spent in discussion and hands-on activities, for which participants used an online collaborative tool (Miro board) to contribute their opinion on the domain landscape. In the following paragraph, first, the agenda of these meetings are presented. Then we present the content of their contribution in the Miro board below and then provide a synopsis of the discussions. Among several agendas, the following were specific to requirement gathering for the domains.

Requirement gathering: The goal of this effort is to identify the set of requirements for ontology development in the domain of interest. To reduce the problem further, it is necessary to take the following steps:

- Identify the focus areas: It is necessary to identify the sub-areas of the domain of interest that needs to be covered by some ontology. Common classification systems, e.g., DFG, ERC may not be suitable from an ontology modelling perspective. Some of the focus areas are already identified from the use cases as they must be covered for demonstration by WP5. These areas are communicated to the participants of the meeting for further expansion.
- identify connections among focus areas: There are overlaps among the sub-areas. Identification of such overlaps may help us in modularizing the ontologies and designing the dependency network (import structure) among different models.

As described in Section 2.1.1, we have conducted structured interviews with each industrial demonstrator, along with use case partners over several weeks. The interviews were organized by WP5 members towards building specification of initial use cases (D5.2) and WP3 task members collaborated with WP5 for gathering use case requirements. The demonstrators received the interview questions in advance and answered them in preparation for the interview. The format of the interview questions was edited in a preparatory internal meeting performed jointly by WP3 and WP5 members. The interviews with each demonstrator took between 30-60 minutes with at least one WP3 member present. During the interviews, the motives of the given questions were discussed and elaborated for eliciting more detailed answers from the industrial partners. In the post-interview period, the answers given by the industrial demonstrators were analysed by WP3 task members to extract both functional and non-functional requirements. The scope and purpose of the use case are also captured from the answers in the corresponding ORSD document.

The third set of meetings was conducted to involve external experts in the domain ontology requirement gathering as described in Section 2.1.2. A series of meetings were scheduled for different focus areas listed in Section 4.2. For each of the focus areas, a primary contact person from the task members took the onus of conducting the meeting by first contacting the list of external experts for a suitable time, scheduling the meeting, and then hosting the meeting. For each meeting, the scope and purpose of the meeting are explained to the participants in the context of the agenda of the OntoCommons project, first. Then a detailed discussion is orchestrated to dive deep into the core requirement of the domain area, the state of current requirements, and the important concepts that need to be addressed. Some of the participants also provided additional materials from their past work. Along with verbal discussions, each meeting also provided an online collaborative board (Miro, Mural etc.) to the participants to write their opinions and take part in the off-line chat. After each of the meetings, the inputs provided by participants (meeting recordings, comments on online

board, and additional materials acquired) are analysed by WP3 task members and a new set of functional and non-functional requirements are added to the domain area level ORSD document.

2.4 Domain classification

An initial list of domain areas in the overall scope of the OntoCommons project, namely, material science and manufacturing (NMBP domains), is derived from the landscape analysis conducted under T3.2 (Le Franc et al., 2022). These domain areas were sourced from three group meetings were organized in May 2021 to gather more ideas about the current shape of the domain ontology landscape and identify gaps (see section 2.1.3 of deliverable D3.2). The focus areas that are identified for material science are properties (e.g., crystallography, tribological, electronic, chemical, mechanical, and structural characteristics), physics-based models (e.g., thermodynamics, continuum, mesoscale, electronic, and phase-field), chemical models (e.g., electrochemical, chemical kinetics, and catalysts), and different types of materials (e.g., alloy, composites, molecular, bio/hybrid, nanomaterial, and powdered material). The focus areas that are identified for mechanical and industrial sectors are design, logistics, manufacturing process, industrial maintenance, product, complex system, system, and supply chain. Next, we investigated the scope of the use cases and the areas covered by them. It is observed that not all areas from this list are sufficiently covered in the use cases, especially lacking coverage in material science. Based on such observations, we determined the following domain areas (Focus Groups) under the scope of domain-level requirement analysis. It is to be noted that the list of domain areas may grow in the future with the addition of new areas or spin-offs from the following areas.

- FG1: Systems Engineering
- FG2: Product and Service
- FG3: Material Science
- FG4: Manufacturing
- FG6: Enterprise
- FG8: Maintenance

2.5 Metrics

During this activity, domain experts and users in collaboration with the ontology development team validate whether the ontology requirements defined in the previous step are correct and complete. The following criteria can be used in this validation task as stated in (Grüninger & Fox, 1995):

- A set of requirements is correct if each requirement refers to some feature of the ontology to be developed.
- A set of requirements can be considered complete if users and domain experts review the requirements and confirm that they are not aware of additional requirements.
- A set of requirements can be considered internally consistent if there are no conflicts between them.
- A set of requirements is verifiable if there is a finite process with a reasonable cost that tests whether the final ontology satisfies each requirement.
- Each requirement must be understandable to end-users and domain experts.

- An ontology requirement is unambiguous if it has only one meaning; that is if it does not admit any doubt or misunderstanding.
- A set of requirements is concise if every requirement is relevant and if there are no duplicated or irrelevant requirements.
- A set of requirements is realistic if every requirement meaning makes sense in the domain.
- A set of requirements is modifiable if its structure and style allow one to change issues in an easy, complete, and consistent way.

It was observed that some of the aforementioned criteria are difficult to apply for requirements addressing loosely delineated domains with many subject areas to address. Especially, it is difficult to decide whether a set of domain requirements are indeed complete for a domain, as domain experts may always come up with new requirements. It is also hard to identify experts who is knowledgeable in all the aspects of a domain to provide such holistic judgement. Completeness criteria, on the other hand, is only suitable for an application case, where users can determine whether a set of CQ is enough to capture their requirements. Naturally, there is a need to weaken the aforementioned evaluation criteria.

Correctness: Since most of the requirements have been extracted from the project's use cases, we can assume that they are correct with respect to the ontologies to be proposed for the use cases.

Completeness: A set of requirements can be considered complete with respect to a specific task if experts reviewing the requirements agree on the suitability of the requirements to fulfil the task.

Consistency: It requires a complete understanding of the elucidation behind each requirement to understand whether there is any conflict. The terms in the CQ may refer to concepts and associated criteria that are different from their dictionary meaning. At this point, we will assume that the requirements are not mature enough to be exposed to these criteria.

Verifiability: This criterion is applicable if we consider all requirements can be expressed as queries over a knowledge base. Most of the CQs can be converted into a SPARQL query. Some of the CQs asking for a definition may need to be reformulated after the sufficient and necessary criteria for the term are determined. Moreover, this criterion also requires appropriate data for the KG to be populated. As we are not fully aware of such data sources, this criterion cannot be fully evaluated. We can assume that the CQs are verifiable provided all necessary resources are available.

Understandability: As requirements have been checked by both use case owners and domain experts involved in the project during online meetings, it can be assumed that the requirements are understandable. Requirements that were considered unclear have been either clarified or removed.

Unambiguity: Considering that OntoCommons adopt a pluralistic approach with purpose to have formal comparisons between different ontologies, committing to the strong criterion of having a single intended meaning is not suitable. The terms and the corresponding hyponym/meronym are not the only way to express the concept but also need reference to a TLO/MLO pre-existing and well-formalised concept. Different TLO and MLO may analyse the concept in different ways. The ambition of this criteria can only be fulfilled if only evaluated by the community that created such requirements. In our case, we will keep the intended meaning open for interpretation based on further investigations in the future.

Conciseness: Duplicate requirements are removed. All use case requirements are relevant because they are needed by the demonstrators. Some of the requirements collected from domain experts may also be useful from the perspective of use cases but it is hard to determine at this point.

Realistic: As all requirements are collected from the use cases or given by domain experts, they are vetted to contain some meaning for the domain.

Modifiability: In principle, there is nothing wrong with changing requirements but, then, one may likely need to change the ontology. Hence, a strategy for managing ontology evolution and versions needs to be in place as proposed in section 3.1

3. Non-functional requirements

3.1 Ontology engineering technical principle

Following the pluralistic approach that OCES, at least 10 domain ontologies built from different sources will be harmonized. Most importantly, at least three new domain ontologies will be developed to cover areas agreed upon by project demonstrators according to the agreement of stakeholders.

Concerning the overall goal of OCES to provide intra- and cross-domain interoperability through a harmonized network of ontology, the stakeholders require a clear and comprehensive guideline for technical management and administration of ontology engineering activities. Although deliverable D4.2 suggests LOT methodology as guidance to ontology engineering stages, we still need to concretize many aspects of development and management principles. This problem is exacerbated by the fact that leaders of different tasks responsible for ontologies for different levels may bring in their practices and protocols. Without such a clear principle, the alignment and development efforts will be difficult to harmonize and coordinate in different work packages and tasks. Furthermore, the need for a common ontology development standard is recommended by several stakeholders and domain experts in past surveys, workshops, and focus group meetings.

In the following, we enlist the aspects (not exhaustive) that are required to be covered by the technical principal document. The final technical principle may be published separately or part of D3.5 to be released in month 29.

3.1.1 Ontology development and alignment

Most of the ontology engineering work in OCES is about alignment which needs to be conducted both vertically (MLO to TLO/TRO, and DLO to MLO) and horizontally (TLO to TLO, MLO to MLO, DLO to DLO).

3.1.2 Language and expressivity

As proposed by OntoCommons, a supported list of languages need to be specified for alignment and development. Though most of the ontologies in MLO and DLO are in OWL, we still need to decide what level of expressivity (OWL Lite/DL/Full) OCES is going to admit. For harmonising TLOs,

the level of rigorousness in logical alignment needs to be urgently (currently ongoing) specified. For such, a suitable language from Common Logic, CASL may need to be specified.

3.1.3 *Reasoner and prover*

Specify which reasoner(s) will be used. OWL-DL specific: Pellet, Hermit, Fact++ etc. FOL specific: Prover9, Hets family...

3.1.4 *Serialization format*

What will be the serialization format in which ontology files will be encoded? (OWL/XML, RDF/XML, JSON-LD, Turtle)

3.1.5 *Mapping relation vocabulary*

Which set of relations will be used for mapping.owl:EquivalentClass, rdfs:subClassOf are stricter. Also, SKOS provides a set of mapping relationship e.g., skos:closeMatch,skos:exactMatch, skos:broadMatch, skos:narrowMatch and skos:relatedMatch

3.1.6 *IRI and naming conventions*

What will be the domain and identifier for the IRI and URI? e.g. <https://ontocommons.eu/...> but we may need to apply persistent URL (purl). It is also required to be specified whether an alphanumeric identifier or lexical identifier will be used.

e.g., http://emmo.info/emmo#EMMO_3f9ae00e_810c_4518_aec2_7200e424cf68 vs <http://emmo.info/emmo#Quantum>

The naming convention for the labels for the terms (both class and relation). for example,OverlappedBy vs Overlapped by vs overlappedBy vs overlapped-by

3.1.7 *Metadata*

(annotation properties) What are the minimum and full list of available metadata to be associated with the ontology and its contents (terms, axioms). Some popular collections are given by owl, rdf, dcat, skos, dcterms, mod.

3.1.8 *Versioning scheme*

How the ontology files will be versioned? What will be the numbering pattern?

3.1.9 *Documentation and visualization*

How an ontology (or alignment) will require to be documented (structure)? What will be the format, e.g., doc, latex, markdown? Relevant tools, e.g., LOD2, widoco? Ontology documentation should include a visual for the model in a specified format, e.g. UML, CHOWLK, or WebVOWL.

3.1.10 Tools, management, review process

For collaborative development, the services provided by ownCloud are not suitable for development. Common development phases need appropriate tools. Following are some suggestions from typical software development.

- Collaboration (Confluence)
- Source code repository (Github)
- CI/CD (Jenkins)
- Issue tracking (JIRA)

How to review, validate and approve development from different members. We may need to set up a review board that will approve development commits for merging. A set of clear quality criteria may also need to be defined.

3.2 Application-level

This section presents the use case-specific scope and purpose, and non-functional requirements. For each use case, the ORSD template (see Section 2.2) is used except for the fields Functional Requirements and Pre-glossary terms. The Functional requirements for the use cases are presented in Section 4.1 and a combined glossary is given in Appendix 1. For more information on the use case partners and their business cases, please refer to deliverable D5.2 Specification of initial cases.

3.2.1 UC1: IRIS - Industrial Co-design Support

1	Purpose
	The use case aims to demonstrate: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - decreased development time via automatized decision making and improved re-usability, - improved reliability via traceability, - improved communication between product, assembly and industrial system experts via data integration and increased domain knowledge interoperability.
2	Scope
	Increase the interoperability and improve the communication between aircraft design, assembly design and industrial system design.
3	Implementation Language and existing standards and ontologies
	OWL
4	Intended End-Users
	Knowledge scientist, System engineering expert, Assembly process engineer, Simulation engineer
5	Intended Uses
	The system is expected to support decision-making during aircraft industrial system design. Some expected benefits include: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Predict behaviour, explore architectural alternatives early in the development process, and

	<p>perform trade studies to assess which design choices make the most sense for manufacturing performance.</p> <p>2) Develop a cognitive twin based on captured domain knowledge, models and simulations.</p> <p>3) Perform a Business transformation that includes new organizations and new roles to develop the models and to perform manufacturing engineering activities.</p>
6	Non-Functional Requirements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This use case will be based on the output of a relevant project (QU4LITY) pilot and the BFO, IOF-Core, QU4LITY, IOF-MBSE models. • Improve the interoperability by aligning the application ontology to the top-level ontology or top reference ontology which is the expected output of OntoCommons.

3.2.2 UC2: SeDIM: Semantic Data Integration for Manufacturing

1	Purpose
	Foster scalable development of Machine Learning (ML) pipelines for condition monitoring of industrial equipment. The use case aims to improve the reusability of existing ML pipelines for similar processes of tasks. The company aims to achieve the adaptation of ML pipelines with affordable, minimal modifications in the existing pipelines.
2	Scope
	For the welding process, one of the typical manufacturing processes, the data of this Use Case are collected from three typical sources: the production plants at OEMs, the laboratories for process development, and simulation in the research centre for a better understanding of the process. The dataset size, i.e., the number of welding spots, ranges from 10 to around 3000.
3	Implementation Language and existing standards and ontologies
	Ontology: Bosch Ontology (developed in-house), QMM-ML Ontology, QMM-Core Ontology, QMM-Domain Ontology, ML Pipeline Ontology
4	Intended End-Users
	Process experts, Measurement experts, Managers, Data managers, Data scientists
5	Intended Uses
	By annotating data with uniformly defined structures and feature names from ontologies, data collected from different conditions, sources or even different processes with similarity can be integrated into a Uniform Data Format. The relational database data in Uniform Data Format will migrate to a triple store in knowledge graph whose knowledge graph schema will integrate the core ontology and domain ontology involved in this use case (welding process).
6	Non-Functional Requirements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combine the ontologies from domain experts and data scientists.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examples of data sources are the production plants at OEMs, the laboratories for process development, simulation in the research centre for a better understanding of the process.
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3.2.3 UC3: Engineering for Procurement

1	Purpose
	The main goal of the use case is to describe data from various sources within the Aibel organization, semantically, in order to 1) improve the reusability of data and processes, 2) find inconsistencies via reasoning in terms of specific requirements, 3) improve interoperability between departments/organizations, and 4) improve interoperability between applications.
2	Scope
	Procedures, fabrication, requirements, materials, standards, procurement, and construction.
3	Implementation Language and existing standards and ontologies
	ISO 15926-14, Material-Core (In-house development), Standards Ontology (In-house development), ChEBI, SKOS, Aibel MMD material ontologies
4	Intended End-Users
	Ontology experts, IT operation, Subject Matter Experts, material technologist
5	Intended Uses
	The main goal of the use case is to describe data from various sources semantically within the Aibel organization.
6	Non-Functional Requirements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The use case will be built on top of the existing ontologies used in the company. The ontologies will be extended in the scope of the use case. The ontologies will be used for semantic modelling of material properties and chemical composition. Existing standards will be converted into ontologies via OTTR templates. Material property and chemical composition semantics are added to material grade ontologies. Data sources used are: Regulatory requirements, Product/Material specification, Production or purchase orders, Product certificate, Design codes, Material standards

3.2.4 UC4: Materials' Tribological characterization

1	Purpose
	The primary goal of the use case is to reduce the number and size of, and time required for experiments, for identifying the behaviour of a material or combination of them (e.g., metal, coating, lubricant) with respect to specific operating conditions. The goal is planned to be achieved via better representation of material experiments, enriching existing data with

	additional background knowledge, easing data retrieval and navigation through related resources.
2	Scope
	The use case will provide ontology-based access to a materials' tribological-related information to abstract from underlying data structures.
3	Implementation Language and existing standards and ontologies
	TribAIn ontology (TribAIn 2.0), EMMO / EMMC, VAR Ontology
4	Intended End-Users
	Tribological expert, Ontology engineer/Semantic technologies expert, Software developer
5	Intended Uses
	We should be able to have an API to query the information of experiments. The information would be represented with adequate ontology terms, but the API would abstract the end-user from the necessary underlying SPARQL queries.
6	Non-Functional Requirements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The goal is planned to be achieved via a common representation of material tribological experiments. • Enriching existing data with additional background knowledge • Easing data retrieval and navigation through related resources. • TribAIn does not cover all the aspects that one might expect to describe all tribological aspects (horizontal extension). • TribAIn does not cover material related data, therefore the extension needs to be done.

3.2.5 UC5: EVMF - European Virtual Marketplace Framework

1	Purpose
	The main goal of this use case is to extend and improve the VIMMP (Virtual Materials Marketplace Project) Ontologies which are at the core of the VIMMP platform that aims to support interoperability between different services and marketplaces in NMBP domains. Improve the VIMMP ontology based on the input from the OntoCommons ecosystem and a wider community. It will also create a basis for the alignment of EMMO top-level ontology with various domain ontologies in the materials domain. An example simple scenario would be describing a Materials modelling software tool for inclusion in a virtual marketplace.
2	Scope
	Materials Modelling (MM)/ MM Software documentation, agents expertise, MM topics.
3	Implementation Language and existing standards and ontologies
	VIMMP Ontologies, EMMO, SWO, VISO, OSMO

4	Intended End-Users
	MM Software developer/distributor, MM software user, industrial end-user, modelling expert ("translator")
5	Intended Uses
	A certain software tool is present on the given marketplace (VIMMP) and its key aspects (capabilities, requirements, i.e., libraries and operating systems, licensing) are presented in a way that is helpful and satisfactory for both users and providers.
6	Non-Functional Requirements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RoMM (Commission et al., 2017), MODA (European Committee for Standardization (CEN), 2018), knowledge and services from VIMMP partners and perspective marketplace providers/users (where with "data" we intend both the terminology used and the concrete assertions made). • Help to discuss and improve the proposed framework, also via interactions with similar initiatives. • Discuss the alignment to EMMO of applied domain ontologies (as those in the use case, that address prototypical needs from digital marketplaces and similar NMBP platforms).

3.2.6 UC6: OAS - Ontology-based yard management

1	Purpose
	The main goal of the use case is to improve the automation of yard management starting with the setup/configuration of a site/yard and improving the effectiveness and responsiveness of decision-making in logistics control systems.
2	Scope
	Yard management, plant logistics, and dispatch automation cover the planning, organisation, control, processing, and supervision of the entire flow of materials and goods.
3	Implementation Language and existing standards and ontologies
	BFO, IOF-Core, PSS ontology, Product-Service System (PSS) Ontology, IOF Core Ontology, Material Ontology (reuse existing), Logistic Ontology (reuse existing), Supply Chain Ontology (reuse existing)
4	Intended End-Users
	Service Designer (yard designer, project manager in OAS), Software designer, Customers (and their clients implicitly)
5	Intended Uses
	The OAS systems will automatically retrieve (trigger) and use the ontology to call the necessary process (e.g. truck identification or weighting process) or to perform a necessary action (e.g. open a terminal barrier, display a message in a terminal, inform the next terminal

	in sequence). The workflow of the actions and processes triggered depend on the types of vehicles involved and the materials carried by the vehicles. To be more interoperable, use ontologies when doing site configuration and yard management.
6	Non-Functional Requirements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardize as many processes devices and communications among devices as possible and have a strong semantic model behind. The OAS systems will automatically retrieve (trigger) and use the ontology to call the necessary process (e.g., truck identification or weighting process) or to perform a necessary action (e.g., open a terminal barrier, display a message in a terminal, inform the next terminal in sequence). The workflow of the actions and processes triggered depend on the types of vehicles involved and the materials carried by the vehicles. The main contribution expected from OntoCommons in the described scenario is supported in the creation/modification of existing ontologies for use in the OAS operation, as well as guidelines to introduce rules in the ontology. Data sources used are internal data sources regarding yard management and logistics; data about process control systems for yard logistic objects and devices; and internal data sources containing data about process control systems for yard logistic objects and devices.

3.2.7 UC7: Feedstock Quality Assurance

1	Purpose
	The main focus of this use case is improving feedstock quality assurance. So far, the quality of feedstock is not objectively quantifiable. A shared formal specification like an ontology could help to identify the main process and material parameters that allow describing the quality objectively. The main expected benefits are: digital representation of the entire mixing process, recognition of previously unknown correlations, deciding on adjustable process parameters, consistent quality of feedstock
2	Scope
	Source materials (chemical composition, quantity of the components, shape and size of the metal powder particles), The quality (homogeneity, reproducibility) of the feedstock, produced parts quality (e.g. dimensions, homogeneity, mechanical properties).
3	Implementation Language and existing standards and ontologies
	BFO, BWMD ontology (mid and domain)
4	Intended End-Users
	Material scientist, Process operator
5	Intended Uses

	So far, the quality of feedstock is not objectively quantifiable. A shared formal specification like an ontology could help to identify the main process and material parameters that allow objectively describing the quality.
6	Non-Functional Requirements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data sources are Source material data, Machine Data (torque, time, temperature), Data of the supplier, Data of analytical analysis, Sensor data, Input from the operator

3.2.8 UC8: Nanomaterials Characterization

1	Purpose
	The main goal of the use case is to bridge the gaps between material characterization and nanosafety domains.
2	Scope
	material science, additive manufacturing, safety exposure
3	Implementation Language and existing standards and ontologies
	EMMO
4	Intended End-Users
	Material scientist, Risk analyst, Exposure measurement operator, Nanoindenter operator, Data scientist
5	Intended Uses
	In the use case, the data collected from exposure and emission measurement devices collected by a risk analyst and the experimental data collected by a nanoindentation engineer will be integrated via domain ontologies and top-level ontologies like EMMO in a triple store with reasoning capabilities. Afterwards, the potential causal relationships between the nanomaterial characterization process and safety risks will be analysed via inference and querying.
6	Non-Functional Requirements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The use case combines data that come from the materials science domain, safety exposure domain and additive manufacturing domain. OntoCommons will provide intra- and cross-domain interoperability of ontologies that will allow for data integration and interoperability. For 3d-printing nanoparticle emissions, not all classes are found in the existing ontologies. Data sources used are emission/exposure measurement instruments data, extraction from nanoindentation instrument and 3D printer slicer

3.2.9 UC9: Ontology-based Maintenance

1	Purpose
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	To create a common formal terminology for diagnosis and repair of the machines manufactured by Adige SpA and to annotate samples of malfunction reports, possible reasons, and machine parts involved, so that semi-automatic analysis of malfunction may be carried out.
2	Scope
	Machine technical information, possible malfunction reasons, diagnosis, maintenance process, and their relationship.
3	Implementation Language and existing standards and ontologies
	DOLCE
4	Intended End-Users
	The client owning the faulty machine, the technician of the company tasked with assisting the client remotely, the technician of the company tasked with repairing the machine.
5	Intended Uses
	This ontology will be used to annotate samples of malfunction reports from clients, their possible reasons and machine parts relevant to the malfunction will be listed. Such a formal report can be also used for purposes like semi-automated analysis of malfunctions and their comparison.
6	Non-Functional Requirements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The ontology-based organization of a vocabulary for maintenance. The alignment of the vocabulary to the DOLCE top-level ontology. • A list of criteria and a modelling comparison for ontological modelling of machine structure and maintenance information. • Data sources are technical design data from CAD, machine documentation, instructional media (e.g., videos)

3.2.10 UC10: Data Integration and Interoperability in Manufacturing

1	Purpose
	Development of ontologies to empower a decision support system for design and procurement of raw materials (billets) for tube production plants. The ontologies that will be developed for the use case aims to unify the data from different departments involved in the procurement process and help the data integration and interoperability. The ontologies will describe data about manufacturing execution, traceability systems and product specifications.
2	Scope
	manufacturing execution, traceability systems, business process, planning and scheduling.
3	Implementation Language and existing standards and ontologies
	None

4	Intended End-Users
	Production supervisor and foreman, production planning department, supervisors and foreman of finishing lines, production operators, product Specification Department, gate and production vehicles operators, information systems in extrusion work centre, production department, weighing platform operator, quality control department, forklift truck operator, information systems in foundry's production process.
5	Intended Uses
	Data mapping, data interoperability, communication improvement, and productivity improvement.
6	Non-Functional Requirements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data sources are ERP, MES, SCADA, Energy Management, Waste Management, Traceability systems and hardware. • Data Mapping - enrich data with context and semantics, optimize reference data management for better classification and categorization of master and operational data. • Data Interoperability – real-time data availability and accessibility to all business units. • Communication Improvement between business units. • Productivity Improvement – increase the timeliness and empower decision-making processes.

3.2.11 UC11: Digital Manufacturing / Automation Engineering

1	Purpose
	The main goal of the use case is to provide a data layer as part of the IoT platforms of Siemens that reduces application/customer-specific data provisioning and integration costs. Also to address the reduction of the efforts of factory automation engineers for accessing engineering data from various disciplines, such as electrical engineering, mechanical engineering or automation software.
2	Scope
	<p>Manufacturing standards, assets (machine, tool, factory, equipment) in automation engineering, data integration.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Overview of existing industry ontologies with relevance for Siemens, the potential for becoming part of the library: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Material data models ○ Equipment / O&G data models (e.g. CFIHOS) ○ Building data models (e.g. BIM) ○ Energy data models (e.g. CIM) ○ Automation data models (e.g. AutomationML, OPC-UA Companion Standards, etc.)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Best practice for data model governance as well as modelling tools (also for domain experts) – Guidelines and best practices for modelling, modularization and maintenance – Training material for developers and other stakeholders.
3	Implementation Language and existing standards and ontologies
	ISO 15936, QuED, SSN, UMATI, eClass, OPC-UA (in-house transformation from the standard), CFIHOS
4	Intended End-Users
	Production supervisor and foreman, production planning department, supervisors and foreman of finishing lines, production operators, product Specification Department, gate and production vehicles operators, information systems in extrusion work centre, production department, weighing platform operator, quality control department, forklift truck operator, information systems in foundry's production process.
5	Intended Uses
	Siemens will develop an ontology library that covers various relevant domain ontologies as well as ontology transformations of various industrial standards. In particular, this library will cover models for assets in the domains of manufacturing and automation engineering. Based on these models, Siemens will showcase a demonstrator for the integrated access to various otherwise disparate automation engineering artefacts that are combined in a scenario in which integrated automation engineering data is being made accessible to technical users to ease their daily work in a heterogeneous landscape of engineering tools.
6	Non-Functional Requirements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO 15926-14 needs to be adopted as a core-reference ontology. May need to align with TLO, SOSA/SSN, QUDT. • Data sources are physical engineering systems, functional engineering systems, electrical Engineering systems, sensors, actuators, control systems, asset management systems, operations monitoring systems, and weather forecast services.

3.3 Domain level

This section presents the scope and purpose, and non-functional requirement for each domain listed in Section 2.4. The ORSD template (see Section 2.2) is used except for the fields Functional Requirements and Pre-glossary terms. The Functional requirements for each domain are presented in Section 4.1 and a combined glossary is given in Appendix 1. Most of the non-functional requirements for the domains are collected from the input of stakeholders and external members. Before the non-functional requirements for each domain is presented in the following sub-sections, the generic requirements discussed during the focus group meetings are presented below.

3.3.1 General requirements for domain ontology development

Ontology as a conceptualization of reality vs information model: The need of ontology is to formalize the terms used by engineers in the manufacturing field. Engineers often find it difficult to change their perspective because they find it difficult to connect their domain-specific view to a global point of view. For example, some ontologies address CAD, but they just classify the elements (point, line, surface, body) in some formal language, e.g., OWL, but these ontologies fail to capture the cognitive understanding that CAD models capture. We are not interested in the ontology being another representational scheme of some existing representational scheme but a way to model the concept that the existing scheme represents. In this sense, ontologies should not be used as another data structure but as the conceptualization of domain knowledge.

As a counterargument, a trade-off approach at the intersection between a foundational view on ontology engineering and an application view is possible as well. The Semantic Web community provides indeed a lot of technical support to handle linked data and knowledge-based representation and reasoning systems where ontologies do play a fundamental role.

On the difficulty of finding existing ontology for reuse: One of the difficulties in reusing the existing ontologies is the difference in the complexity level, they take under their scope. If we want to reuse an existing ontology first determining at which level this ontology falls (domain reference, domain, or application) is a complicated effort. But OntoCommons should provide us with some room to experiment with that.

On the adoption of existing standards for ontology development: According to some ontology experts, since ISO/IEC standards are well known in engineering communities, definitions for concepts may be sourced from these standards. As a counterargument, it is posited that standard definitions are not using ontological terms. We can take the definition and try to define it formally. We need to try to state it differently using ontological terms. The other issue is that some of the terms in the definition take advantage of intuitions. But when subjected to procedural activities it causes a problem because of different viewpoints associated with those terms.

However, it is to be noted that industrial experts may not easily agree with ontologists, especially when the perspectives of the latter seem counter-intuitive or too abstract to domain experts. From this perspective, we assume that an open-minded attitude from both sides is needed. Data exchange, mutual understanding, and interoperability is the ultimate purpose for ontology development. Domain experts need to pay attention to the distinction drawn by ontologists to organize data; on the other hand, ontologists need to pay attention to the engineering use of specific terms and they need to be ready to leave aside their philosophical positions if these do not meet engineering knowledge. Hence, ontologies have to take engineers' points of view and find a good place for them.

Furthermore, we should not talk about the standard only. Every standard has a shelf life and they expire with innovation and progress in understanding. Even if industries are using some standards currently, we must make effort to improve them and make new standards, especially in the context of Industry 4.0.

3.3.2 Manufacturing

1	Purpose
	To establish one or more ontologies (either by aligning existing ontologies or creating new) that captures various taxonomies for the manufacturing process, resources, planning and control, build domain level taxonomies for and capture relationships among these concepts.
2	Scope
	The manufacturing domain will address planning, scheduling, and controlling of processes, resources, factories and shops. The domain will take into account requirements from operations in various applicative industries, such as automotive, aerospace, energy, chemical, food, apparel, agriculture, machining, prototyping and 3D printing, metallurgical, biological, and biochemical.
3	Implementation Language and existing standards and ontologies
	Standards: ISA 95, ISA 88 Formal languages and tools used for manufacturing: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unified Modelling Language (UML) including stereotypes extending UML • Web Ontology Language (OWL) • Object Modeling Language (OML) • System Modelling Language (SysML) • EAST-ADL (Architecture Description Language) • Object Process Methodology (OPM) • Modelica • Karma language, based on a GOPRR (Graph, Object, Point, Property, Role and Relationship) • CAPELLA from PolarSys • Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) • Unified Profile for DoDAF/MODAF (UPDM)
4	Intended End-Users
5	Intended Uses
	Uses of ontology in manufacturing are in 1) manufacturing system design which may be different in different industries (note that resources need to be defined specific to the industry), 2) Different trade-off analyses, for example, alternative architecture, 3) translation from one modelling language to other. 3) Characterization of different processes, for example, modelling historical processes but also processes for which expertise is lacking.
6	Non-functional Requirements
	For the domain reference ontology in manufacturing, we need to fundamentally consider the “intentional transformation of a physical entity to achieve something”, which will include the terminologies for required participants, controllers etc. At the domain level, we should then extend these concepts for different industries say automotive, chemical etc.

	<p>Modelling in discrete manufacturing and continuous manufacturing are different from each other. Discrete manufacturing terms are close to the products but the terms used in continuous manufacturing is different from discrete manufacturing and specific to continuous manufacturing only. In continuous manufacturing, batch and schedules are an important focus.</p> <p>To build a more realistic ontology for the factory, UML state charts may be used, e.g., the resource states. Also, the controllers of the system are required to model. It is also required to model control policy that is enforced in the process control. One system may have more than one control policy and may switch from one to another based on the scheduling need. For configuration, optimization, and planning, we need performance indicators related to the objectives to be achieved.</p> <p>It also needs to be noted that the same terms in manufacturing are used in a different context in different industrial sectors. Also, the same concept may have different terms in different industrial sectors. For example, process, activities, operations, and action, though synonyms, may have the same or different notions in different industries.</p>
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3.3.3 *Materials Science*

1	Purpose
	<p>The materials science domain will address discovery, design, development and application of materials, where materials are any type of matter (natural or man-made) and is understood in the wider sense of including not only solids but also soft matter and liquids.</p> <p>It includes the study of materials and related processes, its structure (from subatomic to macroscale) and behaviour (i.e. properties) at any level of resolution, from electronic structure to continuum, and by any method (all types of materials characterization, modelling and theory) and considering materials manufacturing history and life cycle.</p>
2	Scope
	The requirements would cover the elucidation of all key concepts covering the above, relevant taxonomies and relation
3	Implementation Language and existing standards and ontologies
	OWL, Turtle, RML, RDF, SHACL, OOPs, RepOSE
4	Intended End-Users
5	Intended Uses
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ontology development, Data Transformation Tools fit for Domain Experts, Guidelines and Tutoring for Domain Experts • Use cases showing what can be done using ontologies and how to use them are still missing. • Ontology mapping is only domain-specific and localized which is hindering global interoperability.

6 Non-functional Requirements

- Areas to focus in material science are given in D3.2 (reproduced below in Figure 10)
 - Need to add experimental types and methods.
 - Some quantitative properties could be expressed as a functional relationship between two or more quantities.

Figure 10: Focus areas and dependence hierarchy (arrows pointing from the area that is required to the area that is requiring)

- There is a need for multiple definitions of materials, e.g., composition+structure or synthesis procedure (history). Such different definitions should be enabled to be connected for the "same" material.
- In the definition of material, the transformation of material during manufacturing may also be captured.
- Materials may include both liquid and composites along with solids.
- Materials from all scales may be admitted. Also, not all materials are homogeneous in all scales. Mechanical property may be in focus. It needs to be decided whether to only admit homogeneous elastic properties at macro-scale or nano and microstructural features too. In this sense, material properties may be expressed as hierarchical layers based on scale.
- Material aspects of the lifecycle of an object need to be captured.
- Interoperability between material modelling and simulations need to be established by the ontology.

3.3.4 Systems Engineering

1	Purpose
	Describe meta-models and models for MBSE and process lifecycle

2	Scope
	MBSE models and lifecycle
3	Implementation Language and existing standards and ontologies
	OWL, KARMA
4	Intended End-Users
	tool vendors and industrial MBSE practitioners
5	Intended Uses
	Describe meta-models and models for data integration across the lifecycle
6	Ontology Requirements
	<p>The existing modelling language has some ontological notions behind them. For example, Users of Modelica considers the models as the physical structure definition of a system using DAE and users of OPM make use of some topology between process and object to represent system architecture. However, these languages are not ontology themselves because the model is implied by these languages.</p> <p>SysML 2.0 is being developed in a way that it is grounded in an Ontology as a departure from SysML 1.0, leaving UML behind. However, any kind of system design or simulation language provides a set of constructs based on their features to define the reality and it is assumed that the users will follow the prescribed notion for those constructs.</p> <p>Discreet manufacturing and continuous manufacturing model are not completely separate. Discreet manufacturing may need some continuous modelling, e.g., metal fabrication may need to model the heat generated by the system.</p> <p>There are two aspects, first, the ontology for systems engineering needs to address requirements, interfaces, the system of systems, the logical and functional side of the system etc. and interoperability among them, the second aspect is the interconnection of digital engineering artefacts, e.g. PSpice, finite element analysis. The second aspect is not completely covered by systems engineering and most of them are considered for digital engineering.</p> <p>The boundary of a system can be determined from the causal relationships among the components or environments from the requirements. The point from which a system is viewed is important because the system is a mental construct after all and based on that the same phenomena can be modelled as a closed system or an open system. Such viewpoints come from the problems that the system addressed. Currently, there are many languages to model the solution but no language to model the problem. Also, a problem needs to be modelled from different stakeholders' points of view. Also, it is noted that the problem space not entirely belongs to engineers but also non-engineers who describes the problem space. Requirements are required to be formalized by some languages, but currently, most of the requirements are defined based on natural languages.</p>

The current state of the art does not distinguish between the components of the system, whether they are physical or virtual, tangible or intangible. It is the modeller who represents all the things inside the system that they need.

It is important to note that every system is inside some other system, that every system has an environment. No system stands alone. However, this definition runs into the problem of making the scope too big.

MBSE ontology should consider the differences among the MBSE model, methodology and tools. The tool helps in organizing different concepts regarding systems engineering, for example, MagicGrid prescribes a workflow on top of SysML to organize the design of a system; GOPPRRE ontology represents models from different meta-models.

Some specific requirements for MBSE are:

- The SE ontology and MBSE ontology should define the system (physical), virtual model, concept (like architecture), modelling language and methodology, organization, and lifecycle for the complex system separately.
- Ontology is the main core to support consistency management across different modelling tools.
- MBSE ontology enables the representation of meta-model, meta-meta model, and model.
- MBSE ontology should contain different modelling languages such as SysML, UML, OPM and other graphical specifications.
- MBSE ontology should be supported by different modelling languages.
- MBSE ontology should be represented based on semantic modelling techniques.

MBSE Methodologies:

- STRATA
- RFLP
- DODAF
- MagicGrid
- Arcadia

MBSE languages for complex system design and representation:

- Unified Profile for DoDAF/MODAF (UPDM)
- System Modelling Language (SysML)
- SysML v2 (based on KernML)
- Unified Architecture Framework (UAF)
- CAPELLA from PolarSys
- Unified Modelling Language (UML)
- Modelica
- Object Process Methodology (OPM)
- Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN)
- STRATA from Vitech
- Karma language, based on a GOPPRR (Graph, Object, Point, Property, Role and Relationship)
- Lifecycle Modeling Language (LML)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EAST-ADL (Architecture Description Language) • Architecture Analysis & Design Language (AADL) <p>MBSE Tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Simulink • Amesim • CORE • Capella • GENESYS • Open Meta • Innoslate • Open Modelica • Anylogic • MWORKS • SIMIO • Metagraph • MetaEdit
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3.3.5 *Products and Services*

1	Purpose
	The purpose of the Product and Service (and PSS if appropriate) requirements is to discover or build new ontologies that will support companies in the organisation and alignment of the taxonomies for the Products (e.g. BOM) and Services that they deal with (design, manufacture, sell, use, etc) and the relationships among such Product and Services and other terms (not included in these ontologies/taxonomies) such as manufacturing processes or regulations associated with a specific Product, aiming to build Information model for the applications that will be used in the company.
2	Scope
	Product and Service (and PSS if appropriate) domain will address the whole Product, Service (and PSS if appropriate) lifecycle, from design, manufacturing (discreet), sale, use, etc.
3	Implementation Language and existing standards and ontologies
	EXPRESS language, PSS ontology
4	Intended End-Users
	All possible stakeholders involved in Product(s) and Service(s) lifecycle (from design, development, use, end of life, etc.). These include product manufacturers, suppliers, service providers, users of products and services etc.
5	Intended Uses
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of services around products (so-called Product Extension Services) • Development of cross-sectorial services, using data from products and processes

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product information is used in many processes and phases of a company and this is not always consistent (even within one company). • Industrial Information systems (Internal to the company, and also from belonging to partners and customers) integration • Information or data management for product • Business Analysis • Software Customisation
6	Ontology Requirements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depending on what types of products are being addressed, the ontological concerns may change. For example, a product assembly may require composition whereas materials like polymers need distribution. • The scope of the service may be only services related to the product but also related to various facets of the business (e.g., financial service, consultancy services) for the facilitation of the industry and economy. E.g., financial services are also services that can be used in industry but not particularly related to a Product (not services in PSS only) - these could be a too wide field, therefore the focus should be on Services that are related to the products inside. • The activities for service needs to be captured as well as the resources for these activities, e.g., software tools, human resources, machines, equipment. Resources can be tangible or intangible resources. The unitary resource can only be used by one activity, whereas discreet resources can be used by several activities. • Product and services may not be separated in some cases. E.g., pre-transactional, transactional, and post transactional services are integrated into a product. The services need to be taken into consideration even at the time of designing. This is the concept of PSS. • Lifecycle applies to both product and service. Service is more than just the addition of the functionality to the product it is about how the full solution is offered and how the interaction between different stakeholders within the whole lifecycle of the product. If we are considering Product Service Systems, their lifecycle is more than the lifecycle of Products and Services involved. • Servitization of products is a new practice and needs to be addressed. In this regard, the role and function of products and services need to be delineated. • Definitions used by product service ontology should be understandable to domain experts even when it adopts a domain-independent upper ontology. • Define limits for what an ontology covers or includes, Also, take into account languages, reference models that are well accepted by the industry. • Criteria for something to be a product: A product (for the manufacturing industry) is a Material Object, manufactured to satisfy a need of the market (e.g. to be sold to provide profit and support customers by covering their needs). • Industry (in particular SMEs) often adopt the definitions given by the ERP applications they use.

3.3.6 Maintenance

1	Purpose
	<p>Version 1: Ontological modelling of concepts, procedures, activities, strategies, objects and resources developed or executed to maintain or restore the state and functionality of a system (or part of).</p> <p>Version 2: Concepts of industrial maintenance when information about all technical, administrative and managerial activities and actions that are required in maintenance management. This ontology can be used by maintenance practitioners of the work management process considering maintenance as a process in which work on many assets is identified, planned, scheduled, executed and analysed or used by operators and owners of assets considering the requirements of a specific asset, how it should be maintained over its life, its reliability and the risk that its failure presents to the organization. Ontological modelling of concepts, procedures, activities, strategies, objects and resources developed or executed to maintain or restore the state and functionality of a system (or part of).</p>
2	Scope
	<p>Version 1: Concepts, procedures, activities, strategies, objects and resources devoted to understanding a state of failure and devoted to the evaluation of the state and functionality of a system (or part of) and to the planning and execution of activities aimed to maintain or restore the state and functionality of a system (or part of).</p> <p>Version 2: Structure of equipment to be maintained, spare parts, monitoring activity, failure detection, events, material resources, maintenance actors, technical documents, administrative documents, intervention, maintenance reports, equipment states, equipment life cycle. Concepts, procedures, activities, strategies, objects and resources devoted to understanding a state of failure and devoted to the evaluation of the state and functionality of a system (or part of) and to the planning and execution of activities aimed to maintain or restore the state and functionality of a system (or part of).</p>
3	Implementation Language and existing standards and ontologies
	EN13306, EN17007, ROMAIN, IOF-Maintenance
4	Intended End-Users
5	Intended Uses
6	Non-functional Requirements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • maintenance is one of the activities to keep on fulfilling the purpose of the system. Any change in the part will affect the performance of the larger system it is connected to. The maintenance may be about a particular machine or how the machine interacts with the larger system that includes operators, processes etc.

- Maintenance is not just some activities that are performed on an asset in case of malfunction or failure but it is also a cost-saving strategy. Maintenance is the activity of preserving the quality of the production asset cost-effectively and detecting deviation from the capability.
- Maintenance is a process of preserving the functionality of an asset thereby extending the life of the asset. This aspect of life extension, especially beyond the design life for complex engineered high-value products is lucrative. To support the continuous operability of assets for requirements such as design life extension, it is necessary to monitor various stresses the asset is subjected to and monitor the responses of such actions. It also depends on the business to decide what is the acceptable limit for the maintenance effort based on the recurring cost for replacements and corresponding performance improved in return¹⁰. So it is not only the performance of the machine or equipment but also the value of the asset for the organisation that is being maintained. This also involves maintaining the supporting infrastructure. In that sense, maintenance is not just a routine operation but a careful investigation into finding an optimal solution, which involves efficient planning for improved asset availability. Such requirements were derived from participants' experience in the FMCG sector.
- The maintenance process is initiated by two types of triggers, either a reliability model of the asset or some indicator in the asset itself. We then need to plan for the maintenance activity based on the severity and priority of these triggers. Here we do not need to talk about secondary and tertiary activities involving that asset because they are stopped already¹¹. Then there are various levels: reliability model, continuous reliability growth model¹². The goal is to make sure that the asset is delivering the function at the required state.
- For the general definition of terms (e.g., what is maintenance?), standards such as IEC should be respected. We should start from the requirement of the product and the required function of the components of that product while modelling the domain ontology for maintenance. The clauses which are common to any product are: 1) they are physical assets (software is included but may be controversial) 2) they should satisfy some requirement 3) they should have some functions. Now for maintenance of that product, there should be some specification of actions to restore the components' functions when they lose them. Those actions can be performed at the product level, system level, and component level. It is not recommended to start collecting requirements starting from domain level view but they need to be based on data, e.g., maintenance work order, failure mode analysis. At the same time, it should be noted that some generic notions are applicable across all maintenance, e.g., the notion of state, the notion of maintenance activities (mostly 8 types), CMMS data fields etc.
- Use ROMAIN as a starting point rather than starting from scratch and a number of people agreed that this was what they had thought would happen. Maintenance is not just about restoring function. Many maintenance actions e.g. inspect and service is about 'retaining'

¹⁰ This aspect can be argued, as defence systems for instance are not driven by cost but by performance. Perhaps we could say, 'Businesses do govern the aspects of the levels of maintenance that is relevant based on the requirements of either a performance or a cost or a combinational optimisation model'.

¹¹ I think there is an alternate to this. Yes, there is disruption in the asset operation, however, a maintenance could also lead to secondary unavoidable activity which will become necessary without which the operation will still be left un-operational.

¹² These are almost the same, there are additional factors such as safety, cost, availability and performance.

function. So this sentence is not technically correct 'there should be some specification of actions to restore the components' functions when they lose them". In the modern world (Industry 4.0) we are trying to do actions proactively so that items do not lose their functions, or take much longer to do so. Can we suggest that it is rephrased to "restore or retain the item's function".

- It should be noted that maintenance is not just about the execution phase. >50% of "maintenance" personnel are involved in the strategy, planning, scheduling of maintenance. The ontology must cover this.
- The notion of component is also problematic. Some maintenance just says change the whole item out. This is why the role of a 'maintenance item' is vital for these discussions. Something plays a maintenance item role when it has a strategy and is being managed by the maintenance management process regardless of whether it is a component, subsystem, system, code or software product. Almost all products nowadays have software or embedded code of some description so this has to be included. Managing these complex systems is one of the challenges for maintenance. We cannot exclude this.
- The idea of a purely mechanical system is archaic.
- Terms for a maintenance domain ontology can be related to three parts in relation but which needs to be addressed separately: 1) Items which are being maintained, e.g., Reliability, Maintainability, Required function; 2) maintenance terms, e.g., corrective, preventive, condition-based, predictive, 3) maintenance process, e.g., realization process, support process, management processes.
- EN17007 describes 16 maintenance processes and each process is divided into sub-processes where the inputs/outputs of each of them are indicated, which makes it a complete and generic model of the maintenance process.
- Activities are maintenance activities if they are specified in a maintenance strategy (even if that strategy is to run to failure). I would argue that the addition of requirements and the process of developing/modifying the system to meet new requirements do not fall under the definition of maintenance. For example, is extending the life of a Nuclear Power plant a maintenance activity? Is modifying a plant to fulfil a new regulatory requirement a maintenance activity? Does it need to be known where is the limit of the activity defined as maintenance?
- Maintenance activity may be performed by both human and autonomous machines.
- Maintenance and asset management are not the same where the former is part of the latter.
- The processes involved in software maintenance is much different to asset maintenance/maintenance work management.
- It needs to be argued whether the improvement of an item to fulfil the required function part of maintenance. For instance, by using the feedback from sensors and by improving FMECA models? This is more common in the software industry where the notion of evolutive maintenance is used.
- "a state in which it can perform a required function"- This is important but is difficult to be expressed ontologically. When an asset cannot perform its "function", does the function still exist? Or does the process in which the function is realised a change in some way?¹³

¹³ <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-2969/paper22-FOMI.pdf>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some properties may not be critical for functionality even when it is maintained, e.g., colour. Interpretations about the function of the painting may be different for Airbus and the Quater safety authorities. • What we mean by "state" in maintenance (i.e. failed state) is quite different to the rest of the world's definition of "state". • The maintenance ontology shall help to bring together different types of data to support a process of collective interpretation to take decisions to act on a machine to keep it in operation according to the requirements approved by a design authority. • The maintenance ontology shall be an interface between sources of data and the maintenance users to support their activity. The requirements could start from the expected value of the maintenance ontology, e.g., preserve the meaning of data etc. • Product design may also include maintenance aspects. • Ontologies must work with the data sources they have now. Being able to use data from the CMMS is vital. There are 3 major players - SAP, Maximo and Oracle. All products broadly have the same fields. Key tables in these RDBs are IW39s (in SAP) for MWOs, asset registers, BOMs, strategy PMs, and procedures. The challenge is to integrate these with other data held in other RDBs such as Delay accounting systems, OSI-Pi, production scheduling etc.
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3.3.7 Enterprise

1	Purpose
	Describe models for business management and human resources
2	Scope
	Enterprise organization and human resource management, procurement, supplier, vendor management.
3	Implementation Language and existing standards and ontologies
	OWL
4	Intended End-Users
	Suppliers, vendors, engineers, and legal experts
5	Intended Uses
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structuring data and metadata across the whole procurement process • Human resource assignment (Finding the right person for the right task)
6	Ontology Requirements
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • From the perspective of an enterprise, suppliers and vendors management and the procurement process are related. • The procurement process should be described as a process and not a simple activity. It could refer to the Wikipedia definition "procurement is the process of finding and agreeing to terms, and acquiring goods, services, or works from an external source, often via tendering or competitive binding process". Moreover, the procurement process

depends on the type of industry and the different activities involved in the process; thus its definition could be dependent on the context (i.e., the number of activities). In general, it involves these activities: ordering stock, agreement, selecting potential vendors, sending specifications, and comparing the offers. However, in some cases, if the enterprise has certified vendors, it will use the same activities to buy the product.

- It is important to note that each procurement has its workflow; two different dimensions are included in a procurement process, first, the decision-making/ planning stage (e.g., selecting among alternatives), second, the decision execution stage (e.g., receiving storage). The ontology should separate between the dynamic model (workflow) and the statistical model (the structure of the workflow). Also, an ontology should describe KPI for the assessment of the workflow, such as a vendor evaluation.
- Human resources in the context of procurement depend on the type of planning and execution of the procurement activity in which they participate. For example, the human resource that participates in selecting a vendor, looking to the specification is a very qualified person (i.e., has specific technical qualifications). However, the human resource that executes a procurement process (i.e., tracing the status of the procurement process) doesn't necessarily have technical knowledge. In addition, it might be also some IT systems that could help the different experts for performing different activities (e.g., agreement, selecting offers, etc.) and legal experts that participate in the process.
- It is important to model some specific KPIs for the assessment of the HR performance (related to hiring, firing, promotion, etc.)
- Capturing the hierarchy (levels and departments/ also called functional area) of an enterprise depends on the enterprise policy (there is no standardisation) and the size of the company; small companies don't have a "clear" functional area (i.e; a human can play different roles and be part of the different department). However, enterprises that are in the same industry field, could have the same representation of its hierarchy.
- In the context of an enterprise, the development of scheduling and planning systems are depending on facilities, internal policies, etc. The main problem that needs to be addressed is the inconsistency (different interpretation of the same concept or different values of the same subject) and duplication of the information in many spread systems.
- An enterprise ontology should provide a unique view of the knowledge of the enterprise (i.e., integration of different applications such as ERP) and, more specifically, help identify the "right/adequate" resources for the execution of a particular task.

4. Functional Requirements

4.1 Use case-specific competency questions

After formal and informal interviews with WP5 partners, we collected (in January 2022) in total 341 competency questions with “accepted status” from the use case partners; among them, we observed that 20% (70 CQs) are related to Tekniker use case; 11% (40 CQs) are related to Simens and same for Bosch. The use case Adige SpA provides 9% (34 CQs), Airbus defines 9% (32 CQs), and ElvalHalcor S.A. specifies 8% (30 CQs) and; the other use cases (UKRISTFC and GCL, OAS, and Fraunhofer, and IRES) specifies between 21 to 11 use CQs. Figure 5 details the number of the collected CQs over the 11 use cases.

Figure 11: Distribution of the number of competency questions (with “accepted status”) over the 11 use cases. Average=31 ; Median=31; Max= 70; Min=11 (Results in January 2022).

We observe that 341 of collected CQs (99%) start with the expression “What”; the rest (13 CQs) use the expression “Who?, Which? or How?”. The complete list of CQs for each use case with “accepted status” is presented below.

Each CQ is numbered with the format: UC< use case number>-< CQ serial number>.

4.1.1 UC1: IRIS - Industrial Co-design Support

Identifier	Sprint	Competency Questions	Answer
UC1-1	UC interview	What are the types of resource?	Human resource, intangible resource, material resource

UC1-2	UC interview	What are the types of material ressource?	Equipment, facilities
UC1-3	UC interview	What are the types of equipment?	Drilling adapter, drilling template, measuring equipment, robot, fastener, wedge
UC1-4	UC interview	What are the types of materials?	Manufacturing material, raw material, assembly
UC1-5	UC interview	What are the components of an assembly?	None.
UC1-6	UC interview	What are the types of assembly?	Front fuselage, rear fuselage
UC1-7	UC interview	What types of components are there?	Buttsrap, fastener, frame, stabiliser, stringer
UC1-8	UC interview	What are the functions of different resources?	
UC1-9	UC interview	What are the qualities of different resources?	
UC1-10	UC interview	What are the qualities of different materials?	
UC1-11	UC interview	What are the qualities of different processes?	
UC1-12	UC interview	What are the types of manufacturing and assembly processes?	Boring, cleaning, deburring, drilling, fastening, fixing, insert, inspection, installation
UC1-13	UC interview	What are the functions that are realized by different processes?	
UC1-14	UC interview	What are the required resources of different processes?	
UC1-15	UC interview	What are the required materials of different processes?	
UC1-16	UC interview	What is the information for a system requirement?	Design criteria, design rule, TLR
UC1-17	UC interview	What are the types of system models?	
UC1-18	UC interview	What are the components of a system model?	
UC1-19	UC interview	What are the sub-processes of a design process?	

UC1-20	UC interview	What is the information for a process plan?	
UC1-21	UC interview	What is the information for system design?	
UC1-22	Post-interview	Who are the actors for the industrial system design?	Knowledge scientist, System engineering expert, Assembly process engineer, Simulation engineer
UC1-23	Post-interview	What is the role of a knowledge scientist?	
UC1-24	Post-interview	What is the role of a System engineering expert?	
UC1-25	Post-interview	What is the role of the assembly process engineer?	
UC1-26	Post-interview	What is the role of simulation engineering?	
UC1-27	Post-interview	Based on which decisions design criteria or process configuration is made?	
UC1-28	Post-interview	Which decisions did supersede a decision?	
UC1-29	Post-interview	What are the alternative options for which a decision is to be taken?	
UC1-30	Post-interview	Which are the behaviours an assembly and a system may exhibit?	
UC1-31	Post-interview	What is the type of product?	Manufactured product
UC1-32	Post-interview	What is the requirement for a particular assembly or system?	

4.1.2 UC2: SeDIM: Semantic Data Integration for Manufacturing

Identifier	Sprint	Competency Questions	Answer
UC2-1	UC interview	What are the types of development processes?	Welding machines

UC2-2	UC interview	What are the steps of a process? What is the order between the steps?	
UC2-3	UC interview	What are the types of equipment?	
UC2-4	UC interview	What are the participants of the processes?	
UC2-5	UC interview	What is the target of the process monitoring (condition monitoring)?	
UC2-6	UC interview	What are the types of ML models/templates contained in a pipeline?	
UC2-7	UC interview	What are the components of an ML pipeline?	
UC2-8	UC interview	What are the sources (data flow) of an ML model?	
UC2-9	UC interview	What are the features of ML models?	
UC2-10	UC interview	What are the parameters of equipment?	
UC2-11	UC interview	What conditions are being monitored?	
UC2-14	Post-interview	What are the conditions of equipment that are being monitored?	
UC2-15	Post-interview	Is feature f is part of a feature group g?	
UC2-16	Post-interview	What are the parameters that characterize an ML algorithm?	
UC2-17	Post-interview	What is the explanation that is required from an ML model?	
UC2-18	Post-interview	Who are the actors that are involved in the use case?	Process expert, measurement expert, manager, data manager, data scientist
UC2-19	Post-interview	What is the goal of an RSWOperation?	

UC2-20	Post-interview	Which are the equipment/tools used in RSWOperation?	
UC2-21	Post-interview	What is the goal welding program?	
UC2-22	Post-interview	What is the purpose of a welding machine?	
UC2-23	Post-interview	What are the capabilities of a welding machine?	
UC2-24	Post-interview	What does welding control achieve?	
UC2-25	Post-interview	What is the purpose of a control module?	
UC2-26	Post-interview	What is the purpose of a measurement module?	
UC2-27	Post-interview	What is the purpose of a monitor module?	
UC2-28	Post-interview	What does operation curve current specify?	
UC2-29	Post-interview	What does reference curve current specify?	
UC2-30	Post-interview	What does sheet combination specify?	
UC2-31	Post-interview	Where worksheet bottom is located?	
UC2-32	Post-interview	Where welding spot is located?	
UC2-33	Post-interview	What does QValueSetPoint refer to?	
UC2-34	Post-interview	What does Q-Value measure?	
UC2-35	Post-interview	What are the Adhesive types?	
UC2-36	Post-interview	What is the chassis part of?	
UC2-37	Post-interview	What does Worksheet top refer to?	

UC2-38	Post-interview	What does the Spot diameter measure?	
UC2-39	Post-interview	What does the wear count refer to?	
UC2-40	Post-interview	What does the dress count refer to?	

4.1.3 UC3: SeDIM: Semantic Data Integration for Manufacturing

Identifier	Sprint	Competency Questions	Answer
UC3-1	UC interview	What is the design specification of a plant?	Multiple documents including "Basis for design" and plant and domain-specific specifications.
UC3-2	UC interview	What is the type of clients?	Energy companies.
UC3-3	UC interview	What are the components of a plant?	The plants consist of process cess equipment and infrastructure.
UC3-4	UC interview	What are the functions of the plant?	The plants are typically process plants.
UC3-5	UC interview	Who are the stakeholders of the plant?	Owner, operator, maintainer
UC3-6	UC interview	What are the types of a product?	Pressure retaining products made from metal alloys
UC3-7	UC interview	What are the material components of a product?	Industry-standard material grades, often further specialised with Client "Material data sheet"
UC3-8	UC interview	What are the regulatory requirements?	Safety in design
UC3-9	UC interview	What are the constraints/protocols of these regulations?	Regulatory requirements are laws and regulations. Examples; 2014/68/EU, 2010/26/EU
UC3-10	UC interview	What information are composing regulatory requirements?	Regulatory requirements are laws and regulations. Design in accordance with design codes ensure compliance with regulatory requirements.
UC3-11	UC interview	What are types of materials does a design code designate?	Design codes list industry-standard type material and design rules.

UC3-12	UC interview	What is the relationship between the design codes of a product and its components?	Design codes list industry-standard type material and design rules.
UC3-13	UC interview	What are the types of material grades?	Material grades are industry-standard listed alloy types. Chemical composition, mechanical properties, manufacturing process and testing is typically specified.
UC3-14	UC interview	What are the types of an engineering processes?	Main activities are system design, area design and engineering for procurement
UC3-15	UC interview	Who are the stakeholders of an engineering process?	Client, system engineer, area engineer, package engineer, package buyer, constructor
UC3-16	UC interview	What are the outcomes of the engineering process?	Construction work orders, drawings, requisitions
UC3-17	UC interview	What are the types of a procurement processes?	Issue inquiry, issue purchase orders, expediting, goods receipt, deviation handling
UC3-18	UC interview	Who are the stakeholders of a procurement process?	Package engineer, package buyer, supplier, construction
UC3-19	UC interview	What are the types of a construction processes?	The main activities are fabrication, installation and mechanical completion.
UC3-20	UC interview	Who are the stakeholders of a construction process?	Package engineer, package buyer, construction, client
UC3-21	UC interview	What are the outcomes of construction activities?	A physical plant and its documentation
UC3-22	UC interview	What are the types of a product being certified?	Most product types must have certificates, types of certification differ depending on product type and its use.
UC3-23	UC interview	What are the type of documents (ERP documents: orders, reports, procurement etc.)?	
UC3-24	UC interview	What are the receiving (Destination) and sending (Source) parties of the	

		documents? (agents, department)	
UC3-25	UC interview	What are the fields for these documents?	
UC3-26	UC interview	What is the type of clients?	
UC3-27	UC interview	What are the processes for checking clients' requirements?	
UC3-28	Post-interview	What are the premises for a revision?	
UC3-29	Post-interview	What are the quality factors?	
UC3-30	Post-interview	What is assigned by an ENSteelNumber?	
UC3-31	Post-interview	Does a document have any revisions?	
UC3-32	Post-interview	What are the record rules for an article?	material, Created by, Created with, Created on
UC3-33	Post-interview	What is a compound?	
UC3-34	Post-interview	What is an InanimatePhysicalObject?	

4.1.4 UC4: Materials' Tribological characterization

Identifier	Sprint	Competency Questions	Answer
UC4-1	UC interview	What is an Equipment?	Equipment definition
UC4-2	UC interview	What is a Tribometer	A type of Equipment
UC4-3	UC interview	Which types of Tribometers do exist?	Sliding Tribometer, Rolling Tribometer, Slip-Rolling Tribometer
UC4-4	UC interview	What is a(n) Abrasion tester?	A type of Equipment
UC4-5	UC interview	What is a(n) Tribocorrosion tester?	A type of Equipment
UC4-6	UC interview	What is a(n) Scratch tester?	A type of Equipment
UC4-7	UC interview	What is a(n) Optical microscope?	A type of Equipment

UC4-8	UC interview	What is a(n) Optical profilometer?	A type of Equipment
UC4-9	UC interview	What is a(n) Light Scattering sensor?	A type of Equipment
UC4-10	UC interview	What is a(n) Scanning electron microscope?	A type of Equipment
UC4-11	UC interview	What is a(n) Hardness tester?	A type of Equipment
UC4-12	UC interview	What is a Quality?	Quality Definition
UC4-13	UC interview	What is a(n) Pressure?	A type of Quality
UC4-14	UC interview	What is a(n) O2 level?	A type of Quality
UC4-15	UC interview	What is a(n) Test temperature?	A type of Quality
UC4-16	UC interview	What is a(n) Ambient pressure?	A type of Quality
UC4-17	UC interview	What is a(n) Relative humidity?	A type of Quality
UC4-18	UC interview	What is a(n) Ambient medium?	A type of Quality
UC4-19	UC interview	What is a(n) Radiation type?	A type of Quality
UC4-20	UC interview	What is a(n) Radiation dosage?	A type of Quality
UC4-21	UC interview	What is a(n) pH?	A type of Quality
UC4-22	UC interview	What is Wear?	Wear definition
UC4-23	UC interview	What is a(n) Sliding wear?	A type of wear
UC4-24	UC interview	What is a(n) Slip - rolling wear?	A type of wear
UC4-25	UC interview	What is a(n) Fretting wear?	A type of wear
UC4-26	UC interview	What is a(n) Abrasive wear?	A type of wear
UC4-27	UC interview	What is a(n) Tribo-corrosive wear?	A type of wear
UC4-28	UC interview	What is Geometry?	Definition of Geometry
UC4-29	UC interview	What is a(n) Pin?	A type of Geometry
UC4-30	UC interview	What is a(n) Ball?	A type of Geometry
UC4-31	UC interview	What is a(n) Balls?	A type of Geometry
UC4-32	UC interview	What is a(n) Cylinder?	A type of Geometry
UC4-33	UC interview	What is a(n) Block?	A type of Geometry
UC4-34	UC interview	What is a(n) Plate?	A type of Geometry
UC4-35	UC interview	What is a(n) Disc?	A type of Geometry

UC4-36	UC interview	What is a(n) Ring?	A type of Geometry
UC4-37	UC interview	What is a(n) Sonotrode?	A type of Geometry
UC4-38	UC interview	What is a geometrical arrangement?	Definition of the geometrical arrangement
UC4-39	UC interview	What is a(n) pin-on-disc1?	A type of geometrical arrangement
UC4-40	UC interview	What is a(n) pin-on-disc2?	A type of geometrical arrangement
UC4-41	UC interview	What is a(n) pin-on-disc3?	A type of geometrical arrangement
UC4-42	UC interview	What is a(n) pin-on-disc4?	A type of geometrical arrangement
UC4-43	UC interview	What is a(n) ball-on-plate1?	A type of geometrical arrangement
UC4-44	UC interview	What is a type of movement?	Definition of type of movement
UC4-45	UC interview	What is a(n) sliding?	A type of movement
UC4-46	UC interview	What is a(n) rolling?	A type of movement
UC4-47	UC interview	What is a(n) slip?	A type of movement
UC4-48	UC interview	What is a(n) stick-slip?	A type of movement
UC4-49	UC interview	What is a course of movement?	Definition of course movement
UC4-50	UC interview	What is a(n) continuous?	A type of course movement
UC4-51	UC interview	What is a(n) reversing?	A type of course movement
UC4-52	UC interview	What is a(n) reciprocating?	A type of course movement
UC4-53	UC interview	What is a(n) continuous reversing?	A type of course movement
UC4-54	UC interview	What is a(n) unidirectional?	A type of course movement
UC4-55	Post-interview	What is the standard for a material name?	BS 970, JIS G4805, CAS, DIN 17230, ASTM A295
UC4-56	Post-interview	What are the properties of a material?	Thermal, Electrical, Mechanical, Physical
UC4-57	Post-interview	What is the unit for expressing a property of a material?	
UC4-58	Post-interview	What are the types of material?	Metal, Polymer

UC4-59	Post-interview	What is a model?	
UC4-60	Post-interview	What are the variables of a model?	
UC4-61	Post-interview	What is a procedure?	
UC4-62	Post-interview	What is the strategy of an experiment design?	
UC4-63	Post-interview	What is the field of study?	
UC4-64	Post-interview	What is the hypothesis of an experiment?	
UC4-65	Post-interview	What are the categories of tribological testing?	
UC4-66	Post-interview	What are the samples for an experiment?	
UC4-67	Post-interview	What is the reference of a sample?	
UC4-68	Post-interview	What is the objective of a group of experiments?	
UC4-69	Post-interview	What is the result of an experiment?	
UC4-70	Post-interview	What is a test series?	

4.1.5 UC5: EVMF - European Virtual Marketplace Framework

Identifier	Sprint	Competency Questions	Answer
UC5-1	UC interview	What are the types of software to be used in a virtual marketplace?	Software Tool, Operating system, compiler
UC5-2	UC interview	What are the categories of MM software tools?	simulation engine, post-processing tool, pre-processing tool
UC5-3	UC interview	What are the possible features of a MM software tool?	model feature, solver feature (and a large hierarchy, with classes and individuals, underneath)

UC5-4	UC interview	What are the types of software licenses?	Many, see SWO
UC5-7	UC interview	What are the main constituents of a virtual marketplace platform?	assessment, calendar event, communication, information content entity, infrastructure, interpreter, material, model, process, product, property
UC5-8	UC interview	What are the agents participating in a virtual marketplace?	agent group, data provider, end-user, institution, model provider, software owner, stakeholder, training provider, translator
UC5-9	UC interview	What are the Physical Equations types?	electronic, atomistic, mesoscopic, continuum (actually 25 types, organized into these 4 classes)
UC5-10	UC interview	What are the MM topics?	basic, computational, data, materials, social, theoretical, interdisciplinary, side (actually many, organized into these 8 classes)
UC5-11	Post-interview	What is the programming language for software?	
UC5-12	Post-interview	Who is the distributor of the software?	
UC5-13	Post-interview	What is the identifier of a software version?	
UC5-14	Post-interview	What is a software interface?	
UC5-15	Post-interview	What is a solver?	

4.2 UC6: OAS

Identifier	Sprint	Competency Questions	Answer
UC6-1	UC interview	What are the types of devices?	logistic terminals, sensors, control system, and traffic routing systems and weighing system
UC6-2	UC interview	What are the types of services?	site configuration for yard management and logistics on the warehouse, good/material

			transportation and fleet monitoring, automatic access control of a vehicle
UC6-3	UC interview	What are the types of processes?	truck identification, weighting process, etc.
UC6-4	UC interview	What are the types of actions?	open a terminal barrier, display a message in a terminal, inform the next terminal in sequence
UC6-5	UC interview	What are the types of vehicles?	
UC6-6	UC interview	What are the types of materials?	
UC6-7	UC interview	Which agents are participating in the material transportation?	vehicle driver, access manager, vehicle
UC6-8	UC interview	Which agents are participating in yard management?	
UC6-9	UC interview	Which agents are participating in the fleet monitoring?	
UC6-10	UC interview	Which agents are participating in the automatic access control?	
UC6-11	UC interview	What are the processes involved in the site configuration service?	
UC6-12	UC interview	What are the processes involved in good and material transportation service?	
UC6-13	UC interview	What are the processes involved in the fleet monitoring service?	
UC6-14	UC interview	What are the processes involved in the automatic access control service?	
UC6-15	UC interview	What are the materials carried by different types of vehicles?	
UC6-16	UC interview	What are the actions taken by each device?	
UC6-17	UC interview	What are the processes performed by each device?	
UC6-18	UC interview	What are the constraints/control for each action?	

UC6-19	UC interview	What are the parameters for each service/process?	
UC6-20	Post-interview	What is the information collected for yard management?	Vehicle Load Description, Access Timestamp
UC6-21	Post-interview	What is the material type of a load of a vehicle?	Dangerous material (requires special parking place and treatment), non-dangerous material

4.2.1 UC7: Feedstock Quality Assurance

Identifier	Sprint	Competency Questions	Answer
UC7-1	UC Interview	What are the types of mixing processes?	shaping, casting...
UC7-2	UC Interview	What are the types of materials?	metal, polymer, feedstock, powder
UC7-2a		What is the category (specialization) of a material?	Yes. A categorization exist for each type of material (metal ... etc)
UC7-3	UC Interview	What are the characteristics of metals?	Yes, all are measurable (by machine/ process) -> some examples are provided in the 20 terms. Particle size distribution, Particle shape, Rheological data, Density
UC7-4	UC Interview	What are the steps of the mixing process?	material selection, material characterization, mixing process, feedstock characterization, data correlation, process adjustment, data selection (see all steps in the workflow)
UC7-5	UC Interview	What is the type of quality measurements of a feedstock?	to be specified
UC7-6	UC Interview	What are the mixing parameters to be observed?	Torque, Temperature, Mixing time
UC7-7	UC Interview	What is the type of machine used for mixing?	Blades, Mixer
UC7-8	UC Interview	How many experimentations for a mixing process?	2 round, 3 round ...

UC7-9	UC Interview	What are the actors participating in the mixing process?	material scientist process operator machines and measuring devices
UC7-10	UC Interview	How are materials identified?	Chemical Abstracts Service Registry Number, international labelling standard for chemical substances
UC7-11	UC Interview	How are experiments identified?	Experiment ID (identification no. of the Experiment, e.g. number of the analysis or the trial, LOT Number

4.2.2 UC8: Nanomaterials Characterization

Identifier	Sprint	Competency Questions	Answer
UC8-4	UC interview	What are the measurements collected from the nanoindenter?	hardness and elastic modulus
UC8-5	UC interview	What is the type of nanomaterials?	mostly related to copper nanoparticle
UC8-6	UC interview	What is the outcome of safety exposure measurement?	nanoparticle concentration on the area of 3D printing
UC8-7	UC interview	What are the data collected by risk analysts?	particle concentration
UC8-8	UC interview	What are the data collected from the 3D printer?	nozzle temperature
UC8-9	UC interview	How particle concentration is measured?	Particle number concentration is measured in real-time using direct-reading optical instruments.
UC8-10	UC interview	How to measure/classify risk? What is the definition of risk?	Risk is defined as Hazard*Exposure. Hazard is assessed through the toxicological test (in vitro, in vivo, in silico). Exposure is measured with dedicated instruments and protocols. Specifically for particles, optical and gravimetric instruments are employed.
UC8-11	UC interview	Does having smaller particle has a bigger impact on 3D printers' operators' health?	Smaller particles display higher deposition in more sensitive areas of the respiratory tract (alveoli)

			and the higher surface area leading to increased reactivity.
UC8-12	UC interview	Which software was used for data collection, transfer and analysis?	python, Dropbox API, gcode, nanoindenter software, exposure measurement instruments software
UC8-13	Post-interview	What are the components of a 3D printer?	Nozzle, Filter, Filament
UC8-14	Post-interview	What does the data collected from nanoindenter refer to?	Filament characterization, Printed object
UC8-15	Post-interview	What is PLA (Polylactic acid) used for?	
UC8-16	Post-interview	What is cleaning agent used for?	
UC8-17	Post-interview	What is slicer software used for?	

4.2.3 UC9: Ontology-based Maintenance

Identifier	Sprint	Competency Questions	Answer
UC9-2	UC interview	What kind of laser cutting system is being maintained? What are its functions and behaviours?	FC: the company manufactures machines that are similar to lathes, only they have a cutting head that uses a laser, and not friction, to cut the metal. There are different kinds of such machines, that differ for things such as automation level, dimensions, number of axis of the cutting head, etc. Kinds are identified by different codes, e.g. LT5, LT7,... The description of a single machine in terms of functions and behaviours is too complex to be described briefly, but, if it must be said in a few words, I would say that all of them "cut the tube", and the cutting can be decomposed in "load the tube" (on the machine), "clasp the tube" (with the spindle jaws), "translate and rotate the tube" (with the spindle), "cut the tube" (with the cutting head), "output the cut workpiece" (from the machine)
UC9-5	UC interview	What are the types of reasons/causes that can lead to malfunction?	FC: difficult to say what "cause" is. One could just speak of "failure modes" that cause other failure modes, in such a case refer to UC9-29. Otherwise one could classify causes by the life-cycle step of occurrence: "causes originated during design", "during manufacturing of machine part (by the supplier)", "during assembly of the machine", "during installation of the machine", "during client use of the machine", "during maintenance of the machine".
UC9-6	UC interview	What are the possible types of diagnosis?	FC: Rule-based (if a problem in X arise, then follow steps Y1, Y2,...), Structure-based (if a problem in X

			arise, search within it or nearby it), function-based (if X loses a function F, search for components providing that function)
UC9-7	UC interview	What is the structure of the malfunction solution (Adige) report?	Symptoms, causes, and solutions: the new malfunction solution reports, if implemented, should contain the standard data (e.g. client, technician, date, duration, identifiers of substituted/acted upon components), but, most importantly, fields for symptoms (intended as a set of certain failure modes of relevant components, causes (a selected subset of symptoms), and solutions (e.g. substitution, upgrade, parameter tuning,...))
UC9-8	UC interview	What are the actors/component participating in the maintenance process?	client, field technician, remote technician; faulty component(s), component(s) for replacement (if needed)
UC9-12	UC interview	What are the maintenance solutions?	component replacement, repair, modification, or adjustment (taken from ISO 14224)... Another division is between instance-level solutions (e.g., the substitution of a component) and type-level solutions (e.g., redesign a component or subsystem, because it was badly designed)
UC9-13	UC interview	What is the relation between malfunction and solution?	FC: except for the obvious fact that "a solution solves a malfunction" I don't know
UC9-15	UC interview	What are the spare parts?	They are components not currently installed in a machine.
UC9-16	UC interview	What are the steps for service interaction (company/client)?	The steps for service interaction vary a little between the companies of the group, but in

			<p>general, is as the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Client reports malfunction to company 2. Company remote-service technician collects information and opens a ticket 3. If the problem can be solved remotely, or more information are needed, the technician instructs the client 4. If the problem is solved the ticket is closed with logged info about the events 5. If the problem is not solved a field intervention may be organized, thus a field-service technician is selected and relevant information is shared with him, together with a list of spare parts guessed to be used in the intervention 6. The field intervention is carried out and a report is compiled by the field-service technician 7. If the problem is solved the ticket is closed, as in step 4.
UC9-17	UC interview	What are the types of process relationships?	Force, Heat, etc.
UC9-19	UC interview	What are the types of failure mechanisms?	A physical process used to explain causal propagation between failures modes. Some examples are corrosion, stress
UC9-20	UC interview	What is the type of failure effects?	Failure effects are reduced to failure modes, so their types are the same, and depend on the particular component (see also UC9-29: what is a failure mode)
UC9-21	UC interview	What is the type of failure causes?	Failure causes are reduced to failure modes, so their types are the same, and depend on the

			particular component (see also UC9-29: what is a failure mode)
UC9-22	UC interview	What is the type of maintenance activity?	predetermined maintenance, repairing/corrective maintenance (where repairing subsumes 'diagnosis' and all the maintenance solutions of UC9-12)
UC9-24	UC interview	What is the component of a laser cutting system being maintained?	the laser source, loader, spindle, steady laser, cutting head.
UC9-25	UC interview	What is a component?	any part of a manufacturing machine
UC9-26	UC interview	What are the relations between components?	aggregation (part-of) and structural link (eg electric, hydraulic, pneumatic, kinetic or load-link)
UC9-27	UC interview	What is a function?	The behaviour of a physical object selected by an agent (for a certain goal, in a given context)
UC9-28	UC interview	What is the behaviour of a component?	A set of input and output flows, and the relation between them
UC9-29	UC interview	What is a failure mode (in what ways a component can fail)?	Behaviour that does not realize a function
UC9-30	UC interview	What is the version of a component?	On the meta-level, as a phase of a component, if a component is thought of as a phased sortal. On the application level, there will be a versioned component linked by an "is-new-version-of" relation (eg Motor101_v1.1 is-new-version-of Motor101_v1.0)

UC9-31	UC interview	What is a machine configuration?	A list of optional components.
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4.2.4 UC10: Data Integration and Interoperability in Manufacturing

Identifier	Sprint	Competency Questions	Answer
UC10-1	UC Interview	What are the types of tube?	Billet + Semi-Final (Mother Tube) --> Alloys + Types of Mother Tubes
UC10-2	UC Interview	Is a kind of a tube a specialisation/category of another?	No
UC10-3	UC Interview	What are the dimensions of billets?	Billets have the following dimensions: - 90,0x10,0 -96,5x14,1 -98,0x14,5 -106,0x7,0 -109,0x4,5 -113,0x10,0 -121,0x4x5
UC10-4	UC Interview	How many billets are used for a tube?	One Billet per Mother Tube (1:1 ratio)
UC10-5	UC Interview	What are the components of BOM?	BOM contains : - material code + quantity of semi-final products -material code + quantity of material returns
UC10-6	UC Interview	What is the material constituent of the billet?	Copper & copper alloys
UC10-7	UC Interview	What are the common steps of a production plan?	Forecast Customer Demand --> Receive Orders --> Plan Production --> Check Product Specifications --> Schedule Production --> Calculate Production of Semi-final products --> Calculate billet production --> Send billet order to Foundry --> Calculate Raw material need -->

			Produce billets --> Send billets to Tubes Plant --> Receive Billets
UC10-8	UC Interview	What are the business processes (types)?	[Sales Dpt.] Forecast + Receive Customer Orders --> [Production Planning Dpt.] Plan + Schedule Production --> [Product Specifications Dpt.] Check Product Specifications of orders --> [Production Dpt.] Calculate billet need + make an order to Foundry --> [Foundry] Produce billets + ship them to Tubes Plant --> [Production Dpt.] Extrusion of billets to Mother Tubes
UC10-9	UC Interview	What are the manufacturing processes [types]?	Raw Material Sorting --> Melting --> Casting --> Cutting --> Transportation to Tubes Plant --> Billet Extrusion
UC10-10	UC Interview	What are the kind of machines/equipment/vehicles to be used for the execution of each production step?	Melting Furnace - Casting Equipment - Saw - Trucks - Billet Management Equipment - Preheating + Induction Furnace - Decortiquer - Press
UC10-11	UC Interview	What are the controls for each manufacturing step? (situations at a high level)	-Inventory monitoring - Production and shipment billet quantity monitoring -Weekly Schedule
UC10-12	UC Interview	What is the type of operators/actors that are participating in the process (business, production)?	All actors mentioned in the attached file "UC10_interview questions_rev2"
UC10-13	UC Interview	What are the input/output states for the processes? (high level)	Scrap + Cathode --> Billets --> Mother Tube
UC10-14	UC Interview	What are the type of documents (ERP documents: orders, reports, procurement etc.)?	ERP records --> Daily Scheduling Tool --> Weekly schedule.xls --> E-mail/ Mobile communication --> Traceability System --> SAP system
UC10-15	UC Interview	What are the receiving (Destination) and sending (Source) parties of the	Actors from above

		documents? (agents, department)	
UC10-16	UC Interview	What are the fields for these documents?	Sales Order --> Production Order --> Quantities/Pieces
UC10-17	UC Interview	What are the IT tools (Excel, mail, ERP, SCADA, etc.) used for each business/manufacturing step?	Aforementioned.
UC10-18	UC Interview	What are the tools for control and data acquisition? What type of data/control these tools are managing?	ERP Sales Orders, Inventories etc.
UC10-19	UC Interview	What is the duration of each manufacturing step?	Avg Billet Production time 5 mins, Avg Billet Extrusion time 2 mins
UC10-20	UC Interview	What is the throughput?	400tn/per day Copper billets production --> Transportation to Tubes Plant --> Billet Extrusion --> Production of 31 Mother Tubes per hour
UC10-26	UC Interview	What is the objective for scheduling?	Delivery times, Production Process & Cost optimisation
UC10-27	UC Interview	What are the constraints for scheduling?	Minimum Order Quantity / Manning/ Raw Material availability / Contractual Delivery Times
UC10-28	UC Interview	What is the type of scheduling (single, flow, batch, job)?	Mostly Job Scheduling
UC10-29	UC Interview	Who are the actors of the procurement processes?	Production supervisor and foreman, production planning department, supervisors and foreman of finishing lines, production operators, gate and production vehicles operators, information systems in the extrusion work centre,
UC10-30	UC Interview	Who are the actors of Halcor's Foundry?	production department, weighing platform operator, quality control department, forklift truck operator, information systems in foundry's production process

4.2.5 UC11: Digital Manufacturing / Automation Engineering

Identifier	Sprint	Competency Questions	Answer
UC11-5	UC interview	What are the components of an electrical engineering system (physical, functional, etc.)?	
UC11-6	UC interview	What are the types of equipment?	
UC11-7	UC interview	What are the characteristics of equipment?	
UC11-8	UC interview	What are the functions/capabilities of equipment?	
UC11-9	UC interview	What are the control parameters for some equipment?	
UC11-10	UC interview update	What are the types of an asset?	cable, signallam and PLC card
UC11-14	UC interview	What are the sources of energy/information?	
UC11-15	UC interview	How does the energy flow (distribution) among system components?	
UC11-16	UC interview	What are the types of an automation process?	
UC11-17	UC interview	What are the steps of an automation process?	
UC11-18	UC interview	What are the actors of an automation process step?	
UC11-19	UC interview	What is the input/output of an automation process step?	
UC11-20	UC interview	What modelling tools are used?	
UC11-23	UC interview update	What are the considered standards?	
UC11-24	UC interview update	What is a device?	

UC11-25	UC interview update	What are the components of a device?	
UC11-26	UC interview update	What is the relationship between an automation project and a device?	
UC11-27	UC interview update	What is a channel?	
UC11-28	UC interview update	What is the relationship between a channel and a device item?	
UC11-29	UC interview update	What is a subnet?	
UC11-30	UC interview update	What is the relationship between a subnet and a device?	
UC11-31	UC interview update	What are the types of communication interfaces?	
UC11-32	UC interview update	What is an IO system?	
UC11-33	UC interview update	What is the relation between a communication interface and an IO system?	
UC11-34	UC interview update	What are the types of a port?	
UC11-35	UC interview update	What is the relation between a communication interface and a port?	
UC11-36	UC interview update	What is a PLCBlockGroup?	
UC11-37	UC interview update	What is the relationship between a PLCBlockGroup and CPU?	
UC11-38	UC interview update	What is a Tag?	
UC11-39	UC interview update	What is the relationship between a tag and a channel?	
UC11-40	UC interview update	What is a plcDataTypeGroup?	

4.3 Domain-level ontology requirements

This section presents the list of CQs that describes the functional requirements of each domain, given in Section 2.4. Each CQ is numbered with the format *<domain abbv.>-<CQ serial number>*. For each domain, each CQ is either compiled from use case functional requirements presented in Section 3.2, or collected from the interactions during one of the focus group meetings, described in Section 2.3. For each CQ, the column 'Extracted From' carries the use case CQ in the former case and "FG workshop" in the latter case.

Figure 12: Distribution of the number of competency questions (with "accepted status") over the 6 studied domains. Average= 68; Median=62; Max=144 ; Min=23 (Results in January 2022).

4.3.1 Manufacturing

Identifier	Extracted From	Competency Questions	Answer
MAN-75	UC11-10	What are the types of assets?	cable, signallam and PLC card
MAN-41	UC10-16	What are the fields for these documents (sales order, production order)?	Sales Order --> Production Order -> Quantities/Pieces
MAN-40	UC10-15	What are the receiving (Destination) and sending (Source) parties of the documents?	agents, department
MAN-39	UC10-14	What are the type of documents (ERP documents: orders, reports, procurement etc.)?	ERP records --> Daily Scheduling Tool --> Weekly schedule.xls --> E-mail/ Mobile communication --> Traceability System --> SAP system

MAN-30	UC9-24	What is the component of a laser cutting system?	the laser source, loader, spindle, steady laser, cutting head.
MAN-29	UC9-2	What are the functions and behaviours of a laser cutting system?	FC: the company manufactures machines that are similar to lathes, only they have a cutting head that uses a laser, and not friction, to cut the metal. There are different kinds of such machines, that differ for things such as automation level, dimensions, number of axis of the cutting head, etc. Kinds are identified by different codes, e.g. LT5, LT7,... The description of a single machine in terms of functions and behaviours is too complex to be described briefly, but, if it must be said in a few words, I would say that all of them "cut the tube", and the cutting can be decomposed in "load the tube" (on the machine), "clasp the tube" (with the spindle jaws), "translate and rotate the tube" (with the spindle), "cut the tube" (with the cutting head), "output the cut workpiece" (from the machine)
MAN-73	UC11-8	What are the functions/capabilities of equipment?	
MAN-48	UC4-10	What is a(n) Scanning electron microscope?	A type of Equipment
MAN-19	UC2-10	What are the parameters of equipment?	
MAN-72	UC11-7	What are the characteristics of equipment?	
MAN-49	UC4-9	What is a(n) Light Scattering sensor?	A type of Equipment
MAN-6	UC1-3, UC2-3	What are the types of equipment?	Drilling adapter, drilling template, measuring equipment, robot, fastener, wedge, welding machines
MAN-47	UC4-1	What is an Equipment?	Equipment definition
MAN-10	UC1-10	What are the qualities of materials?	

MAN-7	UC1-4	What are the types of material?	Manufacturing material, raw material, assembly
MAN-25	UC3-13	What are the types of material grades?	Material grades are industry-standard listed alloy types. Chemical composition, mechanical properties, manufacturing process and testing is typically specified.
MAN-31	UC10-1	What are the types of tubes?	Billet + Semi-Final (Mother Tube) --> Alloys + Types of Mother Tubes
MAN-32	UC10-4	How many billets are used for a tube?	One Billet per Mother Tube (1:1 ratio)
MAN-21	UC3-3	What are the components of a plant?	The plants consist of equipment and infrastructure.
MAN-20	UC3-1	What are the design specifications of a plant?	Plant and domain-specific specifications.
MAN-23	UC3-5	Who are the stakeholders of a plant?	Owner, operator, maintainer
MAN-78	UC11-18	What are the actors of an automation process step?	
MAN-79	UC11-19	What is the input/output of an automation process step?	
MAN-80	UC11-26	What is the relationship between an automation project and a device?	
MAN-77	UC11-17	What are the steps of an automation process?	
MAN-28	UC3-20	Who are the stakeholders participating in the construction process?	Package engineer, package buyer, construction, client
MAN-27	UC3-19	What are the types of the construction process?	The main activities are fabrication, installation and mechanical completion.
MAN-36	UC10-11	What are the controls used in a manufacturing process? (situations at a high level)	-Inventory monitoring - Production and shipment billet quantity monitoring -Weekly Schedule
MAN-16	UC2-1	What are the types of development processes?	Welding
MAN-38	UC10-13	What are the input/output states for the processes? (high level)	Scrap + Cathode --> Billets --> Mother Tube

MAN-13	UC1-15	What are the required materials of different processes?	
MAN-65	UC7-7	What is the type of machine used for mixing?	
MAN-67	UC7-6	What are the mixing parameters to be observed?	
MAN-68	UC7-7	What are the type of machines used for mixing?	
MAN-70	UC7-9	What are the actors participating in a mixing process?	material scientist process operator machines and measuring devices
MAN-64	UC7-4	What are the steps of the mixing process?	material selection, material characterization mixing process feedstock characterization data correlation process adjustment data selection (see all steps in the workflow)
MAN-63	UC7-1	What are the types of mixing processes?	shaping, casting...
MAN-52	UC4-44	What are the types of movement?	Sliding, Rolling, Slip, Stick-slip
MAN-26	UC3-16	What are the outcomes of engineering processes?	
MAN-37	UC10-12	What is the type of operators/actors that participate in the business, production?	Production supervisor and foreman, production planning department, supervisors and foreman of finishing lines, production operators, gate and production vehicles operators, information systems in extrusion work centre, production department, weighing platform operator, quality control department, forklift truck operator, information systems in foundry's production process
MAN-14	UC1-20	What is the information a process plan includes?	
MAN-11	UC1-11	What are the qualities of a process?	
MAN-43	UC10-20	What is the throughput of a production line?	

MAN-15	UC2-2	What are the steps of a process? What is the temporal order between the steps?	
MAN-33	UC10-7	What are the steps of a production plan?	Forecast Customer Demand --> Receive Orders --> Plan Production --> Check Product Specifications --> Schedule Production --> Calculate Production of Semi-final products --> Calculate billet production --> Send billet order to Foundry --> Calculate Raw material need --> Produce billets --> Send billets to Tubes Plant --> Receive Billets
MAN-42	UC1--19	What is the duration of each manufacturing step?	Avg Billet Production time 5 mins, Avg Billet Extrusion time 2 mins
MAN-12	UC1-12	What are the types of processes?	Boring, cleaning, deburring, drilling, fastening, fixing, insert, inspection, installation
MAN-34	UC10-9	What are the types of manufacturing processes?	Raw Material Sorting --> Melitng --> Casting --> Cutting --> Transportation to Tubes Plant --> Billet Extrusion
MAN-24	UC3-7	What are the components of a (material) product?	Industry-standard material grades, often further specialised with Client "Material data sheet"
MAN-51	UC4-19	What kind of entity is radiation?	
MAN-50	UC4-15	What kind of entity is Test temperature?	
MAN-2	UC1-8	What are the functions of some resources?	
MAN-5	UC1-2	What are the types of manufacturing resources?	
MAN-4	UC1-14	What are the required resources of different processes?	
MAN-35	UC10-10	What are the kind of machines/equipment/vehicles to be used for the execution of each production step?	Melting Furnace - Casting Equipment - Saw - Trucks - Billet Management Equipment - Preheating + Induction Furnace - Decortiquer - Press
MAN-3	UC1-9	What are the qualities of different resources?	

MAN-1	UC1-1	What are the types of resources?	Human resource, intangible resource, material resource
MAN-45	UC10-27	What are the constraints for scheduling?	Minimum Order Quantity / Manning/ Raw Material availability / Contractual Delivery Times
MAN-44	UC10-26	What is the objective for scheduling?	Delivery times, Production Process & Cost optimisation
MAN-46	UC10-28	What is the type of scheduling (single, flow, batch, job)?	Mostly Job Scheduling
MAN-84	UC11-28	What is the relationship between a channel and a device item?	
MAN-83	UC11-25	What are the components of a device?	
MAN-82	UC11-24	What is a device?	
MAN-81	UC11-20	What modelling tools are used?	
MAN-135	UC1-25	What is the role of the assembly process engineer?	
MAN-136	UC1-26	What are the design criteria for which a process is configured?	
MAN-138	UC1-28	Which are the decisions that superseded a decision?	
MAN-139	UC1-29	What are the alternative options for which a decision is to be taken?	
MAN-140	UC1-30	What are the conditions of equipment that are being monitored?	
MAN-141	UC2-19	What is the goal of an RSWOperation?	
MAN-142	UC2-20	Which are the equipment/tools that used in RSWOperation?	
MAN-143	UC2-21	What is the goal welding program?	
MAN-144	UC2-22	What is the purpose of a welding machine?	
MAN-145	UC2-23	What are the functionalities of a welding machine?	
MAN-146	UC2-24	What does welding control achieve?	
MAN-147	UC2-25	What is the purpose of a control module?	

MAN-148	UC2-26	What is the purpose of a measurement module?	
MAN-149	UC2-27	What is the purpose of a monitor module?	
MAN-150	UC2-28	What does operation curve current specify?	
MAN-151	UC2-29	What does reference curve current specify?	
MAN-152	UC2-30	What does sheet combination specify?	
MAN-153	UC2-31	Where is worksheet bottom located?	
MAN-154	UC2-32	Where is welding spot located?	
MAN-155	UC2-33	What does QValueSetPoint refer to?	
MAN-156	UC2-34	What does Q-Value measure?	
MAN-157	UC2-35	What are the Adhesive types?	
MAN-160	UC2-38	What does the Spot diameter measure?	
MAN-161	UC2-39	What does the wear count refer to?	
MAN-162	UC2-40	What does the dress count refer to?	
MAN-82	FG workshop	Given a product P, what is the amount of each part that is required for manufacturing a specific quantity of P?	
MAN-83	FG workshop	What are the particular executions of a process in a given period?	
MAN-84	FG workshop	What is the role that a given resource plays in the execution of a given process?	
MAN-85	FG workshop	Given a production activity A, what are the activities that have to end in order to A to start their execution?	
MAN-86	FG workshop	Given a production activity A, what are the activities that require the end of A to start their execution?	

MAN-87	FG workshop	Given a material m , which are the tasks that consume it?	
MAN-88	FG workshop	Given a material m , which are the tasks that produce it?	
MAN-89	FG workshop	Given a processing unit j , which are the tasks that such unit can perform?	
MAN-90	FG workshop	Which are the tasks that require a specific utility u ?	
MAN-91	FG workshop	Given a task t , which are the processing units that can perform it?	
MAN-92	FG workshop	Which are the processing units connected to a specific processing unit j ?	
MAN-93	FG workshop	Which are the processing units that are connected to a storage unit k ?	
MAN-94	FG workshop	Given a storage unit k , which materials can be stored in it?	
MAN-95	FG workshop	Which is the dedicated (can only store one material) storage unit?	
MAN-96	FG workshop	Which is the shared (can store more than one material) storage unit?	
MAN-97	FG workshop	Given a material m , which are the storage units that can store it?	
MAN-98	FG workshop	Which are the storage units that are connected to storage unit k ?	
MAN-99	FG workshop	Which are the storage units that are connected to processing unit j ?	
MAN-100	FG workshop	Which are the part types to be produced by a production system under design?	
MAN-101	FG workshop	Which is the components of the part types if the part type is assembled?	
MAN-102	FG workshop	Which are the available process plans to be executed to obtain a part type as output?	

MAN-103	FG workshop	Which are the process steps (operation/tasks) decomposing a process plan?	
MAN-104	FG workshop	Which are the precedence relations between process steps?	
MAN-105	FG workshop	Which is the duration of the process step?	
MAN-106	FG workshop	Is the duration of a process step is deterministic or stochastic?	
MAN-107	FG workshop	Which are the capability requirements of a process step?	
MAN-108	FG workshop	Which selectable production resource type can execute an operation?	
MAN-109	FG workshop	Which are the selectable production resources?	Workstation, transporter, buffer etc.
MAN-110	FG workshop	Which are the properties of a type of machine tool?	
MAN-111	FG workshop	Which is the 3D model of a machine tool?	
MAN-112	FG workshop	What is the purchase cost of a machine tool?	
MAN-113	FG workshop	What are the capabilities of a machine tool?	
MAN-114	FG workshop	Which process steps a machine tool can execute?	
MAN-115	FG workshop	What is the processing time taken by a machine tool to perform a certain process step?	
MAN-116	FG workshop	Which are the possible states of a machine tool?	
MAN-117	FG workshop	What is the energy consumption associated with the possible states of a machine tool?	
MAN-118	FG workshop	What are the failure modes characterized in terms of time to failure and time to repair?	
MAN-119	FG workshop	Which are the production systems included in a certain factory?	
MAN-120	FG workshop	Which are the production resources composing a	Machine tools, buffers, transporters etc.

		production system configuration?	
MAN-121	FG workshop	How are the production resources are connected in a production system?	
MAN-122	FG workshop	Which are the placements of production resources?	
MAN-123	FG workshop	Which is the capacity of a buffer?	
MAN-124	FG workshop	What is the investment cost of a production system?	
MAN-125	FG workshop	Which is the production schedule to be executed in the production system to be involved?	
MAN-126	FG workshop	Which is the planning horizon of a schedule?	
MAN-127	FG workshop	Which production systems are available during the execution of the production plan?	
MAN-128	FG workshop	Which are the scheduled batches?	Part type, quantity
MAN-129	FG workshop	Which is the adopted control policy for a schedule?	
MAN-130	FG workshop	What is the performance of the production system given a production schedule?	
MAN-131	FG workshop	Which are the sources of performance measurement of the production system?	Simulation, analytical method, monitoring?
MAN-132	FG workshop	Which is the throughput (produced quality of each part) of the production system?	
MAN-133	FG workshop	Which are the statistics related to the occupation level of each buffer?	
MAN-134	FG workshop	Which are the statistics related to the evolution of the states of each machine tool?	

4.3.2 Materials Science

Identifier	Extracted From	Competency Questions	Answer
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MAT-1	UC1-1	What is an Equipment?	Equipment definition
MAT-2	UC4-2	What is a Tribometer	A type of Equipment
MAT-3	UC4-3	Which types of Tribometers do exist?	Sliding Tribometer, Rolling Tribometer, Slip-Rolling Tribometer
MAT-4	UC4-4	What is a(n) Abrasion tester?	A type of Equipment
MAT-5	UC4-5	What is a(n) Tribocorrosion tester?	A type of Equipment
MAT-6	UC4-6	What is a(n) Scratch tester?	A type of Equipment
MAT-7	UC4-7	What is a(n) Optical microscope?	A type of Equipment
MAT-8	UC4-8	What is a(n) Optical profilometer?	A type of Equipment
MAT-9	UC4-9	What is a(n) Light Scattering sensor?	A type of Equipment
MAT-10	UC4-10	What is a(n) Scanning electron microscope?	A type of Equipment
MAT-11	UC4-11	What is a(n) Hardness tester?	A type of Equipment
MAT-12	UC4-12	What is a Quality?	Quality Definition
MAT-13	UC4-13	What is a(n) Pressure?	A type of Quality
MAT-14	UC4-14	What is a(n) O2 level?	A type of Quality
MAT-15	UC4-15	What is a(n) Test temperature?	A type of Quality
MAT-16	UC4-16	What is a(n) Ambient pressure?	A type of Quality
MAT-17	UC4-17	What is a(n) Relative humidity?	A type of Quality
MAT-18	UC4-18	What is a(n) Ambient medium?	A type of Quality
MAT-19	UC4-19	What is a(n) Radiation type?	A type of Quality
MAT-20	UC4-20	What is a(n) Radiation dosage?	A type of Quality
MAT-21	UC4-21	What is a(n) pH?	A type of Quality
MAT-22	UC4-22	What is Wear?	Wear definition
MAT-23	UC4-23	What is a(n) Sliding wear?	A type of wear
MAT-24	UC4-24	What is a(n) Slip - rolling wear?	A type of wear
MAT-25	UC4-25	What is a(n) Fretting wear?	A type of wear
MAT-26	UC4-26	What is a(n) Abrasive wear?	A type of wear
MAT-27	UC4-27	What is a(n) Tribo-corrosive wear?	A type of wear
MAT-28	UC5-2	What are the categories of MM software tools?	simulation engine, post-processing tool, pre-processing tool
MAT-29	UC5-3	What are the possible features of a MM software tool?	model feature, solver feature (and a large hierarchy, with classes and individuals, underneath)
MAT-30	UC5-4	What are the types of software licenses?	Many, see SWO
MAT-31	UC5-3	What are the possible features of a MM software tool?	model feature, solver feature (and a large hierarchy, with classes and individuals, underneath)

MAT-32	UC5-9	What are the Physical Equations types?	electronic, atomistic, mesoscopic, continuum (actually 25 types, organized into these 4 classes)
MAT-33	UC5-10	What are the MM topics?	basic, computational, data, materials, social, theoretical, interdisciplinary, side (actually many, organized into these 8 classes)
MAT-34	UC7-2	What are the types of materials?	metal, polymer, feedstock, powder
MAT-35	UC7-3	What are the characteristics of metals?	Yes, all are measurable (by machine/process) -> some examples are provided in the 20 terms. Particle size distribution, Particle shape, Rheological data, Density
MAT-36	UC7-5	What is the type of quality measurements of a feedstock?	Part density, Shrinkage, Dimensional accuracy, Strength
MAT-37	UC7-10	How are materials identified?	Chemical Abstracts Service Registry Number, international labelling standard for chemical substances
MAT-38	UC7-11	How are experiments identified?	Experiment ID (identification no. of the Experiment, e.g. number of the analysis or the trial, LOT Number
MAT-39	UC11-14	What are the sources of energy/information?	
MAT-40	UC11-15	How does the energy flow (distribution) among system components?	
MAT-41	UC8-4	What are the data collected from nanoindenter?	hardness and elastic modulus
MAT-42	UC8-5	What is the type of nanomaterials?	mostly related to copper nanoparticle
MAT-43	UC8-6	What is the outcome of safety exposure measurement?	nanoparticle concentration on the area of 3D printing
MAT-44	UC8-7	What are the data collected by risk analysts?	particle concentration
MAT-45	UC8-8	What are the data collected from a 3D printer?	nozzle temperature
MAT-46	UC8-9	How particle concentration is measured?	Particle number concentration is measured in real-time using direct-reading optical instruments.
MAT-47	UC8-10	How to measure/classify risk? What is the definition of risk?	Risk is defined as Hazard*Exposure. Hazard is assessed through the toxicological test (in vitro, in vivo, in

			silico). Exposure is measured with dedicated instruments and protocols. Specifically for particles, optical and gravimetric instruments are employed.
MAT-48	UC8-11	Does having smaller particle has a bigger impact on 3D printers' operators' health?	Smaller particles display higher deposition in more sensitive areas of the respiratory tract (alveoli) and the higher surface area leading to increased reactivity.
MAT-49	UC8-12	Which software was used for data collection, transfer and analysis?	python, Dropbox API, gcode, nanoindenter software, exposure measurement instruments software
MAT-50	UC3-30	What is assigned by an ENSteelNumber?	
MAT-51	UC3-33	What is a compound?	
MAT-52	UC3-34	What is an InanimatePhysicalObject?	
MAT-53	UC4-59	What is a model?	
MAT-54	UC4-60	What are the variables of a model?	
MAT-55	UC4-61	What is a procedure?	
MAT-56	UC4-62	What is the strategy of an experiment design?	
MAT-57	UC4-63	What is the field of study?	
MAT-58	UC4-64	What is the hypothesis of an experiment?	
MAT-59	UC4-65	What are the categories of tribological testing?	
MAT-60	UC4-66	What are the samples for an experiment?	
MAT-61	UC4-67	What is the reference of a sample?	
MAT-62	UC4-68	What is the objective of a group of experiments?	
MAT-63	UC4-69	What is the result of an experiment?	
MAT-64	UC4-70	What is a test series?	
MAT-65	UC5-11	What is the programming language for software?	
MAT-66	UC5-12	Who is the distributor of the software?	
MAT-67	UC5-13	What is the identifier of a software version?	

MAT-68	UC5-14	What is a software interface?	
MAT-69	UC5-15	What is a solver?	
MAT-70	UC8-15	What is PLA (Polylactic acid) used for?	
MAT-71	UC8-16	What is the cleaning agent used for?	
MAT-72	FG workshop	What are the processes to produce materials?	Casting, Powder Processing, Bulk Deformation Processing
MAT-73	FG workshop	What are the types of binding?	ionic, covalent, and metallic.
MAT-74	FG workshop	What are the crystal systems?	triclinic, monoclinic, orthorhombic, hexagonal, rhombohedral, tetragonal, and cubic.
MAT-75	FG workshop	What are the defects in the microstructure?	Defects in general are simply errors or interruptions in the uniform crystalline lattice.
MAT-76	FG workshop	What are the impurities in the microstructure?	Impurities are atoms (like dirt) that don't belong in the regular crystalline structure.
MAT-77	FG workshop	What are the grains in the microstructure?	Grains are pure crystals or uniform sections of crystal growth.
MAT-78	FG workshop	What are the grain boundaries in the microstructure?	Grain boundaries are boundaries around the separated grains.

4.3.3 Products and Services

Identifier	Extracted From	Competency Questions	Answer
PROD-1	UC1-4	What are the types of materials of a Product?	Manufacturing material, raw material, assembly
PROD-2	UC1-5	What is the component of an assembled Product?	
PROD-3	UC1-19	What are the sub-processes of a design process?	
PROD-4	UC3-7	What are the material components of a product?	Industry-standard material grades, often further specialised with Client "Material data sheet"
PROD-5	UC3-6	What types does a product have?	Types and sub-types of products originating from different production processes
PROD-6	UC3-12	What is the relationship between the design codes of a product and its components?	Design codes list industry-standard type material and design rules.
PROD-7	UC3-22	What are the types of a product being certified?	Most product types must have certificates, types of certification

			differ depending on product type and its use.
PROD-8	UC3-8	What are the regulatory requirements?	Safety in design
PROD-9	UC3-10	What information (Product, Services, components, etc) composes regulatory requirements?	Regulatory requirements are laws and regulations. Product and Service design in accordance with design codes ensure compliance with regulatory requirements.
PROD-10	UC3-9	What are the constraints/protocols of these regulations?	Regulatory requirements are laws and regulations. Examples: 2014/68/EU, 2010/26/EU
PROD-11	UC3-27	What are the processes for checking clients' requirements?	Requirement's compliance makes sure the Products and Services are according to the needs
PROD-12	UC3-11	What are types of materials a design code designates?	
PROD-13	UC3-13	What are the types of material grades?	Material grades are industry-standard listed alloy types. Chemical composition, mechanical properties, manufacturing process and testing is typically specified.
PROD-14	UC3-26	What is the type of clients?	
PROD-15	UC10-1	What are the types of tubes?	Billet + Semi-Final (Mother Tube) --> Alloys + Types of Mother Tubes
PROD-16	UC10-2	Is a certain Product a specialisation/ sub-product/ category of another?	In a factory, many Products and sub-products thereof can be produced
PROD-17	UC10-5	What are the components of BOM?	BOM contains : - material code + quantity of semi-final products -material code + quantity of material returns
PROD-18	UC10-6	What is the material constituent of the billet?	Copper & copper alloys
PROD-19	UC6-2	What are the types of services?	site configuration for yard management and logistics on the warehouse, good/material transportation and fleet monitoring, automatic access control of a vehicle
PROD-20	UC6-12	What are the processes involved in Product and	

		material transportation service?	
PROD-21	UC6-13	What are the processes involved in the fleet monitoring service?	
PROD-22	UC6-14	What are the processes involved in the automatic access control service?	
PROD-23	UC9-16	What are the steps for service interaction (company/client)?	<p>The steps for service interaction vary a little between the companies of the group, but in general, is as the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Client reports malfunction to company 2. Company remote-service technician collects information and opens a ticket 3. If the problem can be solved remotely, or more information are needed, the technician instructs the client 4. If the problem is solved the ticket is closed with logged info about the events 5. If the problem is not solved a field intervention may be organized, thus a field-service technician is selected and relevant information is shared with him, together with a list of spare parts guessed to be used in the intervention 6. The field intervention is carried out and a report is compiled by the field-service technician 7. If the problem is solved the ticket is closed, as in step 4.
PROD-24	UC4-28	What is Geometry?	Pin, Ball, Balls, Cylinder, Block, Plate, Disk, Ring, Sonotrode
PROD-34	UC4-38	What is a geometrical arrangement?	pin-on-disk1, pin-on-disk2, pin-on-disk3, pin-on-disk4, ball-on-plate1
PROD-40	UC4-44	What is a type of movement?	Sliding, Rolling, Slip, Stick-slip

PROD-45	UC5-1	What are the types of software to be used in a virtual marketplace?	Software Tool, Operating system, compiler
PROD-46	UC5-4	What are the types of software licenses needed for a Service?	
PROD-47	UC5-3	What are the possible features of a MM software tool?	model feature, solver feature (and a large hierarchy, with classes and individuals, underneath)
PROD-48	UC5-7	What are the main constituents of a virtual marketplace platform?	assessment, calendar event, communication, information content entity, infrastructure, interpreter, material, model, process, product, property
PROD-49	UC11-10	What are the types of an asset?	
PROD-50	UC1-31	What is the type of product?	Manufactured product

4.3.4 Systems Engineering

Identifier	Extracted From	Competency Questions	Answer
SYS-1	UC1-3	What are the types of equipment?	Drilling adapter, drilling template, measuring equipment, robot, fastener, wedge
SYS-2	UC1-5	What is the component of an assembly?	None.
SYS-3	UC1-6	What are the types of assembly?	The front fuselage, rear fuselage
SYS-4	UC1-16	What is the information for a system requirement?	Design criteria, design rule, TLR
SYS-5	UC1-17	What are the types of system models?	
SYS-6	UC1-18	What are the components of a system model?	
SYS-7	UC1-19	What are the sub-processes of a design process?	
SYS-8	UC1-21	What is the information for system design?	
SYS-9	UC2-3	What are the types of equipment?	
SYS-10	UC2-4	What are the participants of the processes?	
SYS-11	UC2-6	What are the types of ML models/templates contained in a pipeline?	

SYS-12	UC2-7	What are the components of an ML pipeline?	
SYS-13	UC2-8	What are the sources (data flow) of an ML model?	
SYS-14	UC2-9	What are the features of ML models?	
SYS-15	UC2-10	What are the parameters of some equipment?	
SYS-16	UC3-1	– What are the design specification of a plant?	Multiple documents including "Basis for design" and plant and domain-specific specifications.
SYS-17	UC3-3	– What are the components of a plant?	The plants consist of process ccess equipment and infrastructure.
SYS-18	UC3-4	– What are the functions of the plant?	The plants are typically process plants.
SYS-19	UC3-8	– What are the regulatory requirements?	Safety in design
SYS-20	UC3-9	– What are the constraints/protocols of these regulations?	Regulatory requirements are laws and regulations. Examples; 2014/68/EU, 2010/26/EU
SYS-21	UC3-14	– What are the types of an engineering processes?	Main activities are system design, area design and engineering for procurement
SYS-22	UC3-15	– Who are the stakeholders of an engineering process?	Client, system engineer, area engineer, package engineer, package buyer, constructor
SYS-23	UC3-16	– What are the outcomes of the engineering process?	Construction work orders, drawings, requisitions
SYS-24	UC3-27	- What are the processes for checking clients' requirements?	
SYS-25	UC6-1	What are the types of devices?	logistic terminals, sensors, control system, and traffic routing systems and weighing system
SYS-26	UC6-10	Which agents are participating in the automatic access control?	
SYS-27	UC6-14	What are the processes involved in the automatic access control service?	
SYS-28	UC6-18	What are the constraints/control for each action?	
SYS-29	UC9-16	What are the steps for service interaction (company/client)?	The steps for service interaction vary a little between the companies

			<p>of the group, but in general, is as the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Client reports malfunction to company 2. Company remote-service technician collects information and opens a ticket 3. If the problem can be solved remotely, or more information are needed, the technician instructs the client 4. If the problem is solved the ticket is closed with logged info about the events 5. If the problem is not solved a field intervention may be organized, thus a field-service technician is selected and relevant information is shared with him, together with a list of spare parts guessed to be used in the intervention 6. The field intervention is carried out and a report is compiled by the field-service technician 7. If the problem is solved the ticket is closed, as in step 4.
SYS-30	UC9-24	What is the component of a laser cutting system being maintained?	the laser source, loader, spindle, steady laser, cutting head.
SYS-31	UC9-28	What is the behaviour of a component?	A set of input and output flows, and the relation between them
SYS-32	UC8-8	What are the agents participating in a virtual marketplace?	agent group, data provider, end-user, institution, model provider, software owner, stakeholder, training provider, translator
SYS-33	UC11-5	What are the components of an electrical engineering system (physical, functional, etc.)?	
SYS-34	UC11-15	How does the energy flow (distribution) among system components?	

SYS-35	UC11-25	What are the components of a device?	
SYS-36	UC11-14	What are the sources of energy/information?	
SYS-37	UC11-15	How does the energy flow (distribution) among system components?	
SYS-38	UC11-16	What are the types of automation processes?	
SYS-39	UC11-17	What are the steps of an automation process?	
SYS-40	UC11-18	What are the actors of an automation process step?	
SYS-41	UC11-19	What is the input/output of an automation process step?	
SYS-42	UC11-26	What is the relationship between an automation project and a device?	
SYS-43	UC11-20	What modelling tools are used?	
SYS-44	UC11-27	What is a channel?	
SYS-45	UC11-28	What is the relationship between a channel and a device item?	
SYS-46	UC11-29	What is a subnet?	
SYS-47	UC11-30	What is the relationship between a subnet and a device?	
SYS-48	UC11-31	What are the types of communication interfaces?	
SYS-49	UC11-32	What is an IO system?	
SYS-50	UC11-33	What is the relation between a communication interface and an IO system?	
SYS-51	UC11-34	What are the types of a port?	
SYS-52	UC11-35	What is the relation between a communication interface and a port?	
SYS-53	UC11-36	What is a PLCBlockGroup?	
SYS-54	UC11-37	What is the relationship between a PLCBlockGroup and CPU?	
SYS-55	UC11-38	What is a Tag?	

SYS-56	UC11-39	What is the relationship between a tag and a channel?	
SYS-57	UC11-40	What is a plcDataTypeGroup?	
SYS-58	FG workshop	What is a system?	
SYS-59	FG workshop	What is a requirement?	
SYS-60	FG workshop	what is the suggested meta-model for systems of system engineering?	
SYS-61	FG workshop	what is the suggested meta-model for mission engineering?	
SYS-62	FG workshop	what is the suggested meta-model for systems engineering?	
SYS-63	FG workshop	what is a system of systems?	
SYS-64	FG workshop	what is a mission?	
SYS-65	FG workshop	what is a system lifecycle?	
SYS-66	FG workshop	what is a system architecture?	
SYS-67	FG workshop	What is the system's expected operational environment?	
SYS-68	UC1-22	Who are the actors for the industrial system design?	
SYS-69	UC1-24	What is the role of a System engineering expert?	
SYS-70	UC1-26	What is the role of simulation engineering?	
SYS-71	UC1-30	Which are the behaviours an assembly and a system may exhibit?	
SYS-72	UC1-32	What is the requirement for a particular assembly or system?	

4.3.5 Maintenance

Identifier	Extracted From	Competency Questions	Answer
MAIN-1	UC2-3	What are the types of equipment?	Equipment (is the singular and plural) types may be categorised in several ways. Rotating, fixed, electrical, mechanical, electro-mechanical, controls, instrumentation, sensors, etc.
MAIN-2	UC2-10	What are the parameters of equipment?	parameters necessary for protection, control, safety,

			operations, and maintenance, could include state data (machine operating or shutdown) as well as time-series data
MAIN-3	UC2-4	What are the participants of the processes?	Operators, maintainers, reliability engineers, network & data engineers
MAIN-4	UC2-5	What is the target of the process monitoring?	maybe for (automatic) protection, control, operator information, warnings and alarms, predictive maintenance, commissioning or maintenance testing.
MAIN-5	UC2-11	What conditions are being monitored?	Normal or abnormal operating states,
MAIN-6	UC6-4	What are the types of actions?	protection -> trips or controls change the operating envelope, looking for abnormal or anomalous operation beyond normal operation
MAIN-7	UC9-2	What kind of laser cutting system is being maintained? What are its functions and behaviours?	FC: the company manufactures machines that are similar to lathes, only they have a cutting head that uses a laser, and not friction, to cut the metal. There are different kinds of such machines, that differ for things such as automation level, dimensions, number of axis of the cutting head, etc. Kinds are identified by different codes, e.g. LT5, LT7,... The description of a single machine in terms of functions and behaviours is too complex to be described briefly, but, if it must be said in a few words, I would say that all of them "cut the tube", and the cutting can be decomposed in "load the tube" (on the machine), "clasp the tube" (with the spindle jaws), "translate and rotate the tube" (with the spindle), "cut the tube" (with the cutting head), "output the cut workpiece" (from the machine)

MAIN-8	UC9-5	What are the types of reasons/causes that can lead to malfunction?	FC: difficult to say what "cause" is. One could just speak of "failure modes" that cause other failure modes, in such a case refer to UC9-29. Otherwise one could classify causes by the life-cycle step of occurrence: "causes originated during design", "during manufacturing of machine part (by the supplier)", "during assembly of the machine", "during installation of the machine", "during client use of the machine", "during maintenance of the machine".
MAIN-9	UC9-6	What are the possible types of diagnosis?	FC: Rule-based (if a problem in X arise, then follow steps Y1, Y2,...), Structure-based (if a problem in X arise, search within it or nearby it), function-based (if X loses a function F, search for components providing that function)
MAIN-10	UC9-7	What is the structure of the malfunction solution (Adige) report?	Symptoms, causes, and solutions: the new malfunction solution reports, if implemented, should contain the standard data (e.g. client, technician, date, duration, identifiers of substituted/acted upon components), but, most importantly, fields for <u>symptoms</u> (intended as a set of certain failure modes of relevant components, <u>causes</u> (a selected subset of symptoms), and <u>solutions</u> (e.g. substitution, upgrade, parameter tuning,...))
MAIN-11	UC9-8	What are the actors/component participating in the maintenance process?	client, field technician, remote technician; faulty component(s), component(s) for replacement (if needed)
MAIN-12	UC9-12	What are the maintenance solutions?	component replacement, repair, modification, or adjustment (taken from ISO 14224)... Should also include 'servicing' to replenish

			<p>consumables (e.g. lube oil, coolant) and perhaps cleaning.</p> <p>Another division is between instance-level solutions (e.g., the substitution of a component) and type-level solutions (eg redesign a component or subsystem because it was badly designed)</p> <p>Could also include increased monitoring (on-condition maintenance) if a component is degraded but still functional.</p>
MAIN-13	UC9-13	What is the relation between malfunction and solution?	FC: except for the obvious fact that "a solution solves a malfunction" I don't know
MAIN-14	UC9-15	What are the spare parts?	They are components not currently installed in a machine.
MAIN-15	UC9-16	What are the steps for service interaction (company/client)?	<p>The steps for service interaction vary a little between the companies of the group, but in general, is as the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Client reports malfunction to company 2. Company remote-service technician collects information and opens a ticket 3. If the problem can be solved remotely, or more information are needed, the technician instructs the client 4. If the problem is solved the ticket is closed with logged info about the events 5. If the problem is not solved a field intervention may be organized, thus a field-service technician is selected and relevant information is shared with him, together with a list of spare parts guessed to be used in the intervention 6. The field intervention is carried out and a report is compiled by the field-service technician

			<p>7. If the problem is solved the ticket is closed, as in step 4. (The above implies a remote 'field technician' this is often not the case) Question - how do we distinguish spare parts and standby parts or machinery (machinery may be fitted in a redundant configuration, and the 'standby' machinery may be shut down until required for duty (so-called 'cold standby'))?</p>
MAIN-16	UC9-17	What are the types of process relationships?	Force, Heat, etc. Would this also include how energy is transformed? kinetic rotational energy transformed to electrical energy in an electrical generator?
MAIN-17	UC9-19	What are the types of failure mechanisms?	A physical process is used to explain causal propagation between failures modes. Some examples are corrosion, stress
MAIN-18	UC9-20	What is the type of failure effects?	Failure effects are reduced to failure modes, so their types are the same, and depend on the particular component (see also UC9-29: what is a failure mode)
MAIN-19	UC9-21	What is the type of failure causes?	Failure causes are reduced to failure modes, so their types are the same, and depend on the particular component (see also UC9-29: what is a failure mode)
MAIN-20	UC9-22	What is the type of maintenance activity?	How to do this, replace can be both corrective and preventative
MAIN-21	UC9-24	What is the component of a laser cutting system being maintained?	the laser source, loader, spindle, steady laser, cutting head.
MAIN-22	UC9-25	What is a component?	any part of a manufacturing machine
MAIN-23	UC9-26	What are the relations between components?	aggregation (part-of) and structural link (eg electric, hydraulic, pneumatic, kinetic or load -link)
MAIN-24	UC9-27	What is a function?	The behaviour of a physical object selected by an agent (for a certain goal, in a given context)

MAIN-25	UC9-28	What is the behaviour of a component?	A set of input and output flows, and the relation between them
MAIN-26	UC9-29	What is a failure mode (in what ways a component can fail)?	<p>Behaviour that does not realize a function</p> <p>Do not agree - a behaviour may not be desirable but it may not (yet) breach a function, (eg a small leak which is containable)</p> <p>A failure mode is a way a failure presents itself. Leak, seizure, cracking, fracture etc. Also whether the failure is sudden, intermittent or gradual, whether it is hidden or apparent to the operators or maintainers during normal operations.</p>
MAIN-27	UC9-30	What is the version of a component?	<p>On the meta-level, as a phase of a component, if a component is thought of as a phased sortal.</p> <p>On the application level, there will be a versioned component linked by an "is-new-version-of" relation (eg Motor101_v1.1 is-new-version-of Motor101_v1.0)</p> <p>Quite often the difference in parts is termed 'modification' not a version (often a software in industrial applications is also designated modifications).</p> <p>A part may be new, or refurbished (or repaired) for repairable components. There may be a limit on the number of times a component is repaired before it is sentenced to be disposed of or scrapped.</p>
MAIN-28	UC9-31	What is a machine configuration?	A list of optional components.
MAIN-29	FG workshop	What are the life cycle costs of machines owned and operated by our customers?	Use the ontology to identify all the relevant FLs and extract the cost fields for each date and fl and use this to calculate LCC. This needs to be done across different data sets in design, construction, operations.

MAIN-30	FG workshop	In what operating environments are our machines being deployed?	
MAIN-31	FG workshop	What are the most common failure modes experienced by the assets we have sold, or are servicing?	
MAIN-32	FG workshop	Are the failure mode codes in the unstructured corrective maintenance work orders appropriate for the maintainable item that they are assigned to?	
MAIN-33	FG workshop	What work orders generated from fixed interval structured maintenance task specifications are overdue?	
MAIN-34	FG workshop	What were the production circumstances (in DAS and production systems data) associated with the maintenance notification of machine X on date Y?	
MAIN-36	FG workshop	How many breakdown work orders were executed?	Need to use an axiom that says 'only count work orders as being executed if cost or hours > 0"
MAIN-37	FG workshop	How many replace orders were executed before the expected replacement interval <x> of operating hours?	
MAIN-38	FG workshop	What is the total cost of failures on the maintainable item <A> which should have no failures under its scheduled restoration maintenance strategy?	
MAIN-39	FG workshop	Did any scheduled restorations occur before the target interval of <x> operating hours?	
MAIN-40	FG workshop	What is the cost of the work done initiated by an inspection?	First, need to identify inspections: Want to use rules that say only count MWO's that are inspections (extract this information using NLP from the short text), check it was an

			inspection (use \$ amounts to constrain) and check it was done (\$>)). For each of these inspections, log the MWO number. Then locate all other MWO;s initiated by these 'inspection' MWOs and determine the associated costs. Other challenges here with dealing with hierarchies. Usually, inspections are done on equipment or subsystems, not on MIs
MAIN-41	FG workshop	What component or subsystem failed or was maintained? Note this is very challenging if the CMMS functional location field is not identified consistently	Often the item worked on is not properly identified in the MWO. For example, the FL identifies a truck but the MWO text identifies the engine as having the problem. Ontologies can be used to reason if the text, cost, hours etc are consistent with the work being done on the truck or the engine. Note this is a huge issue across all sectors
MAIN-42	FG workshop	Is the classification in the MWO record as activity 'replace' consistent with other fields in the MWO?	Data quality and the ability to use ontologies to automate DQ checks is a good business case for ontologies in maintenance. Knowing if an asset was replaced or not is vital for reliability calculations
MAIN-43	FG workshop	Is the classification in the MWO record as activity 'repair' consistent with other fields in the MWO?	As above
MAIN-44	FG workshop	Is the classification in the MWO record as activity 'inspect' consistent with other fields in the MWO?	As above
MAIN-45	FG workshop	There has been a change in the regulations and an existing permit needs to be modified. Which procedures use this permit and can I update the relevant procedures?	This is a routine manual task done by integrity and reliability engineers everything legislation or rule change. The reasoning is necessary to automate this task.
MAIN-46	FG workshop	I would like to know which procedures describe an end of	This identifies information required for reliability engineers to perform

		life event for my equipment. Which of the procedures contain a "replacement" task (i.e. the replacement of tyres on a truck)?	MTBF calculations. The reasoning is necessary to automate this task.
MAIN-47	FG workshop	Does my inspection procedure check all the failure modes outlined in the Failure Modes and effects analysis (FMEA) that was used in my RCM	This is a routine manual task done by integrity and reliability engineers when inspections are generated after RCM analysis. Reasoning is necessary to automate this task.
MAIN-48	FG workshop	What resources do I require to execute this week's set of procedures?	This is a routine weekly task done by maintenance planners and schedulers. There is no way to easily generate this from the way procedures are currently stored in SAP/ Maximo. Reasoning would make it a trivial step to automate this task.
MAIN-49	FG workshop	What tools, materials and permits do I require to execute a procedure?	This is a routine weekly task done by maintenance planners and schedulers. There is no way to easily generate this from the way procedures are currently stored in SAP/ Maximo. Reasoning would make it a trivial step to automate this task.
MAIN-50	FG workshop	What steps need to be performed to execute my procedure?	This is necessary for interactive tablet/ AR for maintenance technicians.
MAIN-51	FG workshop	Given that I am up to task x, what task needs to be performed next?	This is necessary for interactive tablet/ AR for maintenance technicians.
MAIN-52	FG workshop	Does my assigned procedure have any safety hazards that I need to be aware of?	This is necessary for interactive tablet/ AR for maintenance technicians.
MAIN-53	FG workshop	What corrective action does my procedure suggest on observation of a failure mode in my inspection?	This is necessary for interactive tablet/ AR for maintenance technicians.
MAIN-54	FG workshop	What is an accident?	
MAIN-55	FG workshop	What is an incident?	

4.3.6 Enterprise

Identifier	Extracted From	Competency Questions	Answer
ENT-1	UC1-1	What are the types of resources?	Human resource, intangible resource, material resource
ENT-2	UC1-8	What are the functions of different resources?	
ENT-3	UC1-9	What are the qualities of different resources?	
ENT-4	UC1-14	What are the required resources of different processes?	
ENT-5	UC1-16	What is the information for a system requirement?	Design criteria, design rule, TLR
ENT-6	UC3-5	Who are the stakeholders of the plant?	Owner, operator, maintainer
ENT-7	UC3-15	Who are the stakeholders of an engineering process?	Client, system engineer, area engineer, package engineer, package buyer, constructor
ENT-8	UC3-18	Who are the stakeholders of a procurement process?	Package engineer, package buyer, supplier, construction
ENT-9	UC3-20	Who are the stakeholders of a construction process?	Package engineer, package buyer, construction, client
ENT-10	UC3-8	What are the regulatory requirements?	Safety in design
ENT-11	UC3-9	What are the constraints/protocols of these regulations?	Regulatory requirements are laws and regulations. Examples; 2014/68/EU, 2010/26/EU
ENT-12	UC3-10	What information are composing regulatory requirements?	Regulatory requirements are laws and regulations. Design in accordance with design codes ensure compliance with regulatory requirements.
ENT-13	UC3-27	What are the processes for checking clients' requirements?	
ENT-14	UC3-17	What are the types of a procurement processes?	Issue inquiry, issue purchase orders, expediting, goods receipt, deviation handling
ENT-15	UC3-22	What are the types of a product being certified?	
ENT-16	UC3-27	What are the processes for checking clients' requirements?	
ENT-17	UC3-26	What is the type of clients?	

ENT-18	UC6-2	What are the types of services?	Site configuration for yard management and logistics on the warehouse, good/material transportation and fleet monitoring, automatic access control of a vehicle
ENT-19	UC6-12	What are the processes involved in good and material transportation service?	
ENT-20	UC6-13	What are the processes involved in the fleet monitoring service?	
ENT-21	UC6-14	What are the processes involved in the automatic access control service?	
ENT-22	UC6-19	What are the parameters for each service/process?	
ENT-23	UC6-7	Which agents are participating in the material transportation?	
ENT-24	UC6-9	Which agents are participating in the fleet monitoring?	
ENT-25	UC6-10	Which agents are participating in the automatic access control?	
ENT-26	UC6-8	Which agents are participating in yard management?	
ENT-27	UC6-18	What are the constraints/control for each action?	
ENT-28	UC6-12	What are the processes involved in good and material transportation service?	
ENT-29	UC9-16	What are the steps for service interaction (company/client)?	<p>The steps for service interaction vary a little between the companies of the group, but in general, is as the following:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Client reports malfunction to company 2. Company remote-service technician collects information and opens a ticket 3. If the problem can be solved remotely, or more information are

			<p>needed, the technician instructs the client</p> <p>4. If the problem is solved the ticket is closed with logged info about the events</p> <p>5. If the problem is not solved a field intervention may be organized, thus a field-service technician is selected and relevant information is shared with him, together with a list of spare parts guessed to be used in the intervention</p> <p>6. The field intervention is carried out and a report is compiled by the field-service technician</p> <p>7. If the problem is solved the ticket is closed, as in step 4.</p>
ENT-30	UC10-7	What are the common steps of a production plan?	<p>Forecast Customer Demand --> Receive Orders --> Plan Production --> Check Product Specifications --> Schedule Production --> Calculate Production of Semi-final products --> Calculate billet production --> Send billet order to Foundry --> Calculate Raw material need --> Produce billets --> Send billets to Tubes Plant --> Receive Billets</p>
ENT-31	UC10-10	What are the kind of machines/equipment/vehicles to be used for the execution of each production step?	<p>Melting Furnace - Casting Equipment - Saw - Trucks - Billet Management Equipment - Preheating + Induction Furnace - Decortiquer - Press</p>
ENT-32	UC10-11	What are the controls for each manufacturing step? (situations at a high level)	<p>-Inventory monitoring</p> <p>- Production and shipment billet quantity monitoring</p> <p>-Weekly Schedule</p>
ENT-33	UC10-17	What are the IT tools (Excel, mail, ERP, SCADA, etc.) used for each business/manufacturing step?	
ENT-34	UC10-19	What is the duration of each manufacturing step?	<p>Avg. Billet Production time 5 mins,</p> <p>Avg. Billet Extrusion time 2 mins</p>

ENT-35	UC10-12	What is the type of operators/actors that are participating in the process (business, production)?	All actors mentioned in the file "UC10_interview questions_rev2"
ENT-36	UC10-14	What are the type of documents (ERP documents: orders, reports, procurement etc.)?	ERP records --> Daily Scheduling Tool --> Weekly schedule.xls --> E-mail/ Mobile communication --> Traceability System --> SAP system
ENT-37	UC10-15	What are the receiving (Destination) and sending (Source) parties of the documents? (agents, department)	
ENT-38	UC5-4	What are the types of software licenses?	Many, see SWO
ENT-39	UC5-7	What are the main constituents of a virtual marketplace platform?	assessment, calendar event, communication, information content entity, infrastructure, interpreter, material, model, process, product, property
ENT-40	UC8-8	What are the agents participating in a virtual marketplace?	agent group, data provider, end-user, institution, model provider, software owner, stakeholder, training provider, translator
ENT-41	UC11-10	What are the types of an asset?	cable, signallam and PLC card
ENT-42	UC11-23	What are the considered standards?	FG workshop
ENT-43	UC6-20	What is the information collected for yard management?	FG workshop

5. Evaluation of requirements for domains

5.1 Manufacturing

The requirements in the manufacturing domain concern manufacturing resources and their functions and behaviours, processes, and planning. Several CQs describing specific production machines and equipment were derived from the use case-specific requirements. At the domain level, these can all be considered as resources or assets. Some CQs are also included to describe factory related terms. CQs related to functionalities of these resources for different manufacturing operations are also

included. A detailed model for the behaviour and capability of these resources need to be developed at the domain level. Not enough CQs are present to fully characterize such models.

Similarly, many manufacturing processes are mentioned in the CQs as specified by the use cases. It is to be noted that upper-level terms for both resources and processes need to be characterized at the domain level in such a way that varieties of specific resources and processes applied in different industries for different types of products can be classified in a taxonomy. Related to processes, some CQs also capture a few process indicators. Depending on the process types, many other process indicators may also be available in the manufacturing domain.

Quite a few CQs also include the requirement to address the planning and scheduling of production operations. These activities need detailed knowledge of the necessary resources for the particular tasks at hand. These tasks are normally dictated by the product specifications and design. Such relations are not fully captured by the CQs. However, the given CQs covers the temporal ordering and other relationships required to be established among processes, to some extent. Related to planning and scheduling, some other CQs also mention the need to represent various documents and analytics for management and decision making.

5.2 Materials Science

Most of the requirements in material science are collected from use cases and therefore focus on the specific requirements of the use cases. These areas include experiments using a specific instrument, characterization of processes related to a specific application, and supporting infrastructure, such as simulation, workflow, software used in material science. At the domain level, areas given in the non-functional requirements in Section 3.3.3 need to be covered for a comprehensive set of domain ontologies for material science. The current set of CQs is not enough for such purposes. Requirement analysis, therefore, needs to be conducted for each of these areas separately.

5.3 Systems Engineering

The ontology for systems engineering needs to address requirements, interfaces, the system of systems, the logical and functional side of the system etc. The current set of CQs addresses these concepts at the definition level, indicating these concepts need to be included in the ontology. However, detailed characterizations for these concepts are not given in the current CQs in detail. Some other CQs are specific to use cases related to some specific system. It needs to be investigated how the specific system components and their properties can be classified under general concepts of systems engineering. Systems engineering and Model-based systems engineering (MBSE) is a highly specialized subject matter which needs the various objects and their relationships from a distinct view called system thinking. Therefore, the CQs need to be investigated by systems engineering practitioners during ontology development. Several methodologies and tools for systems engineering are mentioned in Section 3.3.4. During the ontology developments, elucidations for the concepts related to systems engineering may be derived from their use in these methodologies.

5.4 Products and Services

The product and services area concerns the details of products and services that are integrated into a product at pre-transactional, transactional, and post transactional levels. The current set of CQs include requirements for many different characteristics of a product, including product design and specifications. Some CQs also include complex product-related information such as bill of material and characterization of product in terms of production processes and documentation. However, the current CQs do not cover the service-related aspects except some CQs that are specific to yard management, fleet monitoring, procurement etc. which are mostly specific to use cases.

5.5 Maintenance

As part of the non-functional requirement for the maintenance domain, it is mentioned in Section 3.3.6 that three aspects in the maintenance domain need to be addressed separately: 1) Items that are being maintained, 2) maintenance terms, 3) maintenance process. Some of the CQs, given in Section 5.5, related to equipment, laser cutting system for example, and their components may address the first aspect, however, additional qualifications, such as assets, resources, maintainable items may need to be assigned to such equipment. Several CQs related to the maintenance terms, e.g., malfunction, failure, breakdown, safety hazard, accident, and incidents are included. For the third item, several CQs are included related to maintenance processes, e.g., diagnosis, service interaction, servicing, inspection, restoration, repair, maintenance actions and activities. Some other CQs also address the documentations, e.g., maintenance work orders, permits, and analyses, e.g., failure mode and effect analysis (FMEA), CMMS functional location, DAS and production system data, malfunction solution report, related to maintenance activities. However, it is to be noted that more CQs may be needed to characterise each of these concepts completely. Some existing standards and ontologies mentioned in the non-functional requirement in Section 3.3.6 can be consulted for such investigations.

5.6 Enterprise

This area covers various enterprise-level business activities e.g., procurement, supply-chain, human-resource management, supplier and vendor relationships. Each of these areas covers varieties of activities, KPIs and associated resources that are managed by different departments of an enterprise. Naturally, business practices developed over the years gave rise to vast knowledge on the practices and protocols for effective management. The current CQs do not cover them in detail. However, these CQs may be considered sufficient for addressing the particular need for the current use cases. For elaboration on the concepts, various ERP applications and existing data models may be consulted.

6. Conclusions

This report presents the domain level requirements as specifications for the ontology exploitation and harmonization under OntoCommons ecosystem. Considering the vast scope of this effort, as detailed in Section 1.2, this task posed many challenges as the requirements were to be collected

from varieties of sources that asked for expertise in many different domains. The set of requirements presented in this report will be used to identify suitable existing domain ontologies for harmonization as well as develop new ontologies as part of activities to be conducted in Task 3.4 (see Section 1.3). However, these requirements may also provide input for future ontology developments in the domains of materials and manufacturing outside of OntoCommons project.

The requirements were collected closely following a standardized ontology engineering methodology (LOT) with some adjustments to fit the purpose of covering a wide range of domains. The methodology is detailed in Section 2. We adopted a bottom-up approach by first collecting the requirements from the use cases submitted by demonstrators of OntoCommons and then expanded them for various domains. The complex workflows for the process are given in Figures Figure 4Figure 5. For encoding the requirements, a number of standardized templates are used as explained in Section 2.2. The requirements were collected through a number of workshops and meetings, totalling 17, with participation from use case owners, partners, project members and domain experts, including from outside the projects. Besides, the task members met bi-weekly for the past three months to analyse, plan, and organize the requirements.

Section 3 and 0 presents the non-functional and functional requirements respectively for both use cases and domain areas. Section 3.1 also include a list of technical requirements that needed to be decided before the ontology harmonization and development. The non-functional requirements for both use cases and domain areas include scope and purpose, stakeholders and end-users, a list of related data standards, tools, and existing ontology models, and important topics in the form of general methodology, instructions, and directives. Section 0 presents the functional requirements in the form of competency questions separately for each use case and each domain area, such as manufacturing, materials science, systems engineering, products and services, maintenance, and enterprise.

The domain-level requirements collected in this report is evaluated based on a set of evaluation criteria as well as subjective judgement in Section 5. However, the criteria for the metrics given in Section 2.5 could not be applied rigorously due to the vastness of the domain and lack of consensus on the view of the domains. Several rationales for a weakened version of these metrics are provided. For a more accurate evaluation, especially for determining the completeness of the requirements, the domain areas considered in this report need to be decomposed into smaller and more manageable sub-areas. At the same time, more requirements need to be collected to increase the coverage of these areas. A glossary of terms extracted from the competency questions is included in Appendix 1. In the future, this list of terms may be compared against a standard set of terms (gold standard) for a domain to determine the degree of completeness of the requirements for that domain. For including more detailed requirements for the domains, existing literature on ontology developments in these areas may also be explored in the future. The state-of-the-art survey published as part of D3.2 (Le Franc et al., 2022) may be referred to for that purpose.

The issues will be addressed in the second version of domains ontology requirements and specifications (D3.5) to be published in 29th month of OntoCommons project. A set of further use cases provided by new demonstrators will also provide more requirements for the existing and new domain areas. This report (D3.4) focus on the current use case requirements and prioritize inputs from internal and external domain experts for collecting the requirements. This effort could not be

completed without the invaluable contributions and continuous support from the members of task 3.3 and work package 3 in general as well as external experts and domains stakeholders.

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A. Appendix 1

Glossary of terms (Version 1, 163 simple terms) containing most relevant terms (from A to Z) selected from the functional requirements of all the studied domains. Source indexes the competency question(s) from which a term is extracted (the abbreviation "UC" refers to use case and "CQ" refers to the competency question).

	Term	Source
A	Abrasio+C+B2: B44	UC4Q4, UC4Q5, UC4Q6, UC4Q11
	Accident	MAIN-54
	Acquisition	UC10Q18
	Action	UC6Q4, UC6Q16, UC6Q18
	Actor	UC1Q22, UC2Q18, UC9Q8, UC10Q12, UC10Q15, UC10Q29, UC7Q9, UC11Q18
	Agent	UC6Q7, UC6Q9, UC6Q10, UC5Q8, UC8Q16
	Alveoli	UC8Q11
	Ambient	UC4Q16
	Arrangement	UC4Q38, UC4Q39, UC4Q40, UC4Q41, UC4Q42, UC4Q43
	Article	UC3Q32
	Assembly	UC1Q5
	Asset	UC11Q10
	Automatic	UC6Q10, UC6Q14
	Automation	UC11Q16, UC11Q17, UC11Q18, UC11Q19, UC11Q26
B	Behaviour	UC9Q20
	BOM	UC10Q5
C	Capability	UC11Q8
	Cause	UC9Q5, UC9Q21
	Certification	UC3Q22
	Channel	UC11Q27, UC11Q28, UC11Q38
	Characteristic	UC7Q3, UC11Q7
	Chassis	UC2Q36
	Cleaning	UC8Q16
	Client	UC3Q2, UC3Q26, UC3Q27
	Communication	UC11Q30
	Component	UC1Q5, UC2Q7, UC3Q3, UC3Q12, UC3Q7, UC9Q23, UC5Q7, UC11Q5, UC11Q15, UC11Q25, UC8Q13
	Compound	UC3Q33
	Concentration	UC8Q6
	Condition	UC2Q11, UC2Q14
	Configuration	UC6Q11, UC9Q31
Constituent	UC10Q6	
Constraint	UC3Q9	

	Consumption	MAN-117
	Continuous	UC4Q50, UC4Q53
	Control	UC2Q24, UC2Q25, UC6Q10, UC6Q14, UC6Q18, UC10Q11, UC10Q18, UC11Q9
	Cutting	UC9Q2, UC9Q24
D	Decision	UC1Q28, UC1Q29
	Deposition	UC8Q11
	Design	UC1Q19, UC1Q21, UC1Q22, UC3Q1, UC3Q11, UC3Q12
	Destination	UC3Q24, UC10Q5
	Device	UC6Q1, UC6Q16
	Diagnosis	UC9Q5
	Dimension	UC10Q3
	Document	UC3Q23, UC3Q24, UC3Q26, UC3Q31, 10Q14, 10Q15, 10Q16
	Dosage	UC4Q20
	Duration	UC10Q19
	E	Effect
Electron		UC4Q10
Energy		UC11Q14, UC11Q15
Engineer		UC1Q25
Engineering		UC1Q24, UC1Q26, UC3Q14, UC3Q15, UC3Q16, UC11Q5
Environment		SYS-67
Equipment		UC1Q3, UC2Q3, UC2Q10, UC2Q14, UC2Q20, UC4Q1, UC10Q8
Execution		MAN-85
Expert		UC1Q24
F	Factor	UC3Q29
	Failure	UC9Q19, UC9Q20
	Feature	UC2Q9, UC2Q15, UC5Q3
	Feedstock	UC7Q5
	Field	UC3Q25, UC9Q4, UC10Q16, UC9Q11, UC10Q16
	Fleet	UC6Q9, UC6Q13
	Flow	UC2Q8, UC11Q15
	Foundry	UC10Q30
	Fretting	UC4Q25
	Function	UC1Q8, UC1Q13, UC3Q4, UC9Q2, UC11Q8
G	Geometry	UC4Q28, UC4Q29, UC4Q30, UC4Q31, UC4Q32, UC4Q33, UC4Q34, UC4Q35, UC4Q36, UC4Q37
	Goal	UC2Q19, UC2Q21
H	Hardness	UC4Q4, UC4Q5, UC4Q6, UC4Q11
	Health	8Q11
	Humidity	UC4Q17
I	Identification	UC7Q10, UC7Q11
	Incident	MAIN-55
	Information	UC1Q16, UC3Q10, UC11Q14

	Input	UC10Q13, UC11Q19
	Inspection	MAIN-40
	Instrument	UC8Q9
	Interaction	UC9Q16
	Interface	UC11Q32, UC11Q33, UC11Q35
L	Lifecycle	SYS-65
M	Machine	UC2Q22, UC2Q23, UC7Q7
	Maintenance	UC9Q8, UC9Q12, UC9Q22
	Malfunction	UC9Q9, UC9Q5, UC9Q6, UC9Q11, UC9Q13
	Management	UC6Q8, UC6Q20
	Marketplace	UC5Q1, UC5Q7
	Material	UC1Q4, UC3Q11, UC3Q13, UC6Q6, UC6Q7, UC6Q12, UC6Q15, UC6Q21, UC10Q6, UC7Q2, UC7Q10
	Measurement	UC2Q26, UC7Q5, UC8Q6, UC8Q9
	Mechanism	UC9Q19
	Medium	UC4Q18
	Microscope	UC4Q7, UC4Q10
	Microstructure	MAT-75
	Mission	SYS-64
	Model	UC1Q18, UC2Q6, UC2Q8, UC2Q9, UC2Q17
	Modelling	UC11Q20
	Monitoring	UC2Q5, UC2Q11, UC2Q14, UC2Q27, UC6Q9, UC6Q13
Movement	UC4Q44, UC4Q45, UC4Q46, UC4Q47, UC4Q48	
N	Nanoindentation	UC8Q3
	Nanoindenter	UC8Q4
	Nanomaterial	UC8Q5
O	O2	UC4Q14
	Operation	UC2Q19, UC2Q20, UC2Q28
	Order	UC2Q2
	Outcome	UC3Q16
	Output	UC10Q13, UC11Q19
P	Parameter	UC2Q11, UC2Q14, UC6Q19, UC7Q6, UC11Q9
	Participant	UC2Q4
	Particle	UC8Q7, UC8Q9
	Period	MAN-82
	PH	UC4Q21
	Pipeline	UC2Q6, UC2Q7
	PLA	UC8Q15
	Plan	UC1Q20, UC10Q7
	Platform	UC5Q7
	Port	UC11Q34, UC11Q35
Precedence	MAN-104	

	Premise	
	Pressure	UC4Q13
	Process	UC1Q11, UC1Q12, UC1Q13, UC1Q14, UC1Q15, UC1Q20, UC1Q25, UC2Q1, UC2Q2, UC2Q4, UC3Q14, UC3Q15, UC3Q16, UC3Q17, UC3Q18, UC3Q19, UC3Q20, UC3Q27, UC6Q3, UC6Q12, UC6Q13, UC6Q14, UC6Q16, UC6Q19, UC9Q8, UC9Q17, UC10Q7, UC10Q12, UC10Q13, UC10Q29, UC10Q29, UC7Q1, UC7Q4, UC7Q7, UC7Q8, UC7Q9, UC7Q4, UC11Q16, UC11Q16, UC11Q17, UC11Q18, UC11Q19
	Product	UC1Q31, UC3Q6, UC3Q7, UC3Q12, UC3Q22
	Production	UC10Q7, UC10Q10, UC10Q12
	Profilometer	UC4Q8
	Program	UC2Q21
	Project	UC11Q26
	Protocol	UC3Q9
	Purpose	UC2Q22, UC2Q25, UC2Q26, UC2Q27
Q	Quality	UC1Q9, UC1Q10, UC1Q11, UC3Q29, UC4Q12, UC4Q13, UC4Q14, UC4Q15, UC4Q16, UC4Q17, UC4Q18, UC4Q19, UC4Q20, UC21, UC7Q5
	Quantity	MAN-82
R	Radiation	UC4Q19
	Reactivity	UC8Q11
	Reciprocating	UC4Q52
	Record	UC3Q23
	Regulation	UC3Q8, UC3Q9, UC3Q10
	Relative	UC4Q17
	Report	UC9Q7, UC9Q11
	Requirement	UC1Q16, UC1Q32, UC3Q8, UC3Q10, UC3Q27
	Resource	UC1Q1, UC1Q2, UC1Q8, UC1Q9, UC1Q14
	Reversing	UC4Q51
	Revision	UC3Q28, UC3Q31
	Role	UC1Q23, UC1Q24, UC1Q25, UC1Q26
	Rule	UC3Q32
S	Scanning	UC4Q10
	Schedule	MAN-126
	Scratch	UC4Q6
	Sensor	UC4Q9
	Service	UC6Q12, UC6Q12, UC6Q13, UC6Q14, UC6Q19
	Simulation	UC1Q26
	Site	UC6Q11
	Slicer	UC8Q17
	Software	UC5Q1, UC5Q2, UC5Q3, UC5Q4, UC8Q12, UC8Q17
	Solution	UC9Q7, UC9Q12, UC9Q13

	Source	UC3Q24, UC10Q15, UC11Q14, UC2Q8
	Specification	UC3Q1
	Spot	UC2Q32, UC2Q38
	Stakeholder	UC3Q5, UC3Q15, UC3Q18, UC3Q20
	Standard	UC11Q23
	Step	UC2Q2, UC10Q7, UC10Q10, UC10Q11, UC10Q17, UC10Q19, UC7Q4, UC11Q17
	Storage	MAN-95
	Subnet	UC11Q29
	System	UC1Q16, UC1Q17, UC1Q18, UC1Q22, UC1Q24, UC1Q30, UC1Q32, UC9Q24, UC11Q32, UC11Q33
T	Target	UC2Q4
	Temperature	UC4Q15
	Template	UC2Q6
	Test	UC4Q15
	Tester	UC4Q4, UC4Q5, UC4Q6, UC4Q11
	Throughput	UC10Q20
	Tool	UC2Q20, UC10Q17, UC10Q18, UC5Q2, UC11Q20
	Transportation	UC6Q7, UC6Q12
	Tribocorrosion	UC4Q4, UC4Q5, UC4Q6, UC4Q11
	Tribometer	UC4Q2, UC4Q3
	Tube	UC10Q1, UC10Q4
	U	Unidirectional
Usage		UC5Q1
V	Vehicle	UC6Q5, UC6Q15, UC6Q21
	Version	UC9Q30
W	Wear	UC4Q22, UC4Q23, UC4Q24, UC4Q25, UC4Q26, UC4Q27, UC2Q39
	Welding	UC2Q21, UC2Q22, UC2Q23, UC2Q24, UC2Q25, UC2Q32
Y	Yard	UC6Q8, UC6Q20